

Deliverable 7.1

Intermediate Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIDA	AI-Driven Discovery Assistant
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BASE	Bielefeld Academic Search Engine
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CMS	Content Management System
CNCI/JNCI	Category/Journal Normalized Citation Impact
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DGA	Data Governance Act
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC DIH	EOSC Digital Innovation Hub
EPOS	European Plate Observing System – Dataportal
ESS	Earth System Science
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FCR	Field Citation Ratio
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GraphRAG	Graph Retrieval-Augmented Generation

IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IDS-RAM	International Data Spaces Reference Architecture Model
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPL	Innovation Prototyping Lab
JNCI	Journal Normalized Citation Impact
JUST data	Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, and Transparent data
LLM	Large Language Model
LUMEN	Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network
LUMIS	LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
MATHS	Mathematics
MD	Molecular Dynamics
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
OSDF	Open Science Data Federation
PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
PSNC	Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center
R&D	Research and Development
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RCR	Relative Citation Ratio
SaaS	Software as a Service
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TRIPLE	TRIPLE Project (Horizon Project)
USP(s)	Unique Selling Proposition(s)
WL	White-Label (Discovery Platform)
WP7	Work Package 7

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	6
2. Introduction.....	7
3. Methods.....	8
3.1. Methodology for Market Research in LUMEN.....	8
3.2. Methodology for Defining Preliminary Sustainability Pathways.....	12
4. Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes.....	13
4.1. LUMEN white label platform.....	13
4.2. Federation of platforms.....	17
4.3. LUMIS.....	22
4.4. AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA).....	27
4.5. Interdisciplinary Meta-Search-Service.....	31
4.6. Metrics Service.....	36
4.7. Advanced Visualisation Tools.....	39
4.8. EOSC Innovation Centre.....	42
5. Overview of sustainability modes.....	47
5.1. Structural Long-Term Models.....	48
5.2. Market or service-based models.....	52
5.3. Hybrid Models.....	56
6. Preliminary sustainability pathways for Project outcomes.....	56
6.1. Sustainability Perspectives for Project Outcomes.....	56
6.2. IPL Workshop - Discussing Sustainability Pathways.....	62
7. Summary of efforts towards exploitation of LUMEN outcomes.....	68
7.1. LUMEN exploitation strategy.....	68
7.2. Exploitation activities undertaken so far.....	70
8. Conclusions.....	72
9. References.....	73
10. Annex.....	75
10.1. Working document: overview of sustainability modes.....	75
10.2. Table of competitors considered during competitor analysis.....	78
10.3. Competitor analysis for white label platform.....	81

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the intermediate exploitation and sustainability strategy for the LUMEN project as of December 2025, establishing a foundation for maximising the impact and long-term viability of project outputs. As outlined in the Description of Action, D7.1 provides the initial exploitation plan and roadmap, including outcomes of comprehensive market analysis and business opportunity exploration.

Strategic Context and Objectives. LUMEN addresses critical challenges in research discovery and interdisciplinary collaboration across Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), Mathematics (Maths), Earth System Science (ESS), and Molecular Dynamics (MD) domains. This intermediate report identifies pathways to translate project innovations into sustainable services that will continue serving the European research community beyond the project's lifetime.

Key Achievements. The report progresses through three core activities: (1) identification of key project outcomes with exploitation potential, including the white-label discovery platform, FAIR Semantic Management Space, multiplatform innovative features, and data mesh architectural framework; (2) systematic market analysis examining existing discovery platforms, semantic tools, and AI-powered research services; and (3) exploration of sustainability models applicable to research infrastructure services, drawing on established frameworks and reference cases.

Market Analysis and Competitive Positioning. The market analysis examines existing discovery platforms and their respective strengths, from comprehensive databases like [OpenAlex](#) to discipline-specific services. LUMEN's white-label approach offers adaptability for domain-specific needs while building on proven [GoTriple](#) technology. The analysis identifies potential value propositions for different stakeholder groups, though significant work remains to validate these through stakeholder engagement and use case testing planned for later project phases.

Business Model Framework. Drawing on the EU Innovation Management framework, the report presents a taxonomy of sustainability models applicable to LUMEN outputs, ranging from institutional membership structures to hybrid public-private partnerships. Different outcomes may require distinct business models tailored to their user communities.

Next Steps. This strategy will be refined through stakeholder engagement, Innovation Prototyping Labs, and use case validation (M18-M36). The final strategy (D7.2) will present detailed business models, governance structures, and implementation roadmaps for post-project sustainability.

2. Introduction

Sustainability of developed solutions is key to achieving long-term impact of Horizon Europe funded projects. Yet, sustainability is also a substantial challenge for outcomes of project-funded work. This challenge is commonly encapsulated in finding the right balance within the triangle between viability, desirability, and feasibility of project outputs.

For the specific context of LUMEN, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) federation plays an important part in considerations of sustainability. While it is clear that the final LUMEN services would ideally be integrated and sustained by the EOSC, the EOSC itself is under development. At present, there is insufficient clarity on the exact steps required to secure this sustainability pathway. As a consequence, LUMEN must also consider a range of other options, to ensure that the outcomes developed throughout the course of the project can be sustained beyond the project's lifetime.

This report summarises our efforts within the first year of LUMEN towards achieving sustainability and meaningful exploitation of key LUMEN outcomes. We deliberately speak of “key LUMEN outcomes” in this deliverable, since it is too early in the project to define the final set of Key Exploitable Results. Our work so far has been conducted in three phases:

1. Selection, clarification and elaboration of key outcomes
2. Market analysis of key outcomes
3. Initial considerations on sustainability

The result of step (1) is a set of key outcomes that we analyse in this report:

- LUMEN White Label Platform
- Federation of Platforms
- LUMIS - LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
- AI-Driven Discovery Assistant
- Interdisciplinary Meta-Search Service
- Metrics Service
- Advanced Visualisation Tools
- EOSC Innovation Centre

The report is structured as follows: First, we give a brief overview of the methods we employed for market analysis and sustainability considerations. Next, we present results from the market analysis on all above outcomes, structured by key steps in the process: clearly defining each outcome, results from competitor analysis, results

from SWOT and PESTLE analysis, and key considerations regarding functional requirements, Unique Selling Proposition, and key takeaways. We then provide results from desk research on potential sustainability models, structured into grant-based, structural, or market and service-based models. Based on this overview, we then discuss potential sustainability pathways specific to each outcome. Finally, we provide an overview of the LUMEN exploitation strategy, and activities towards exploitation undertaken so far.

3. Methods

3.1. Methodology for Market Research in LUMEN

The methodology in this deliverable is fundamentally sequential: one step produces information that is necessary for the next step. This sequential methodology is described in the following:

1) Defining Visions for LUMEN Outcome

As a first step, we defined vision documents for all LUMEN outcomes. This was done to establish conceptual clarity regarding each outcome's scope, intended value, target users, and underlying assumptions before analysing the external landscape. A defined vision provides a baseline understanding of what each outcome aims to achieve and is necessary for determining which competitors are relevant and how to interpret their positioning. For this, we shared documents with the responsible outcome leads, including a pre-formulated summary of the outcome and guiding questions on the following topics: core value proposition, key benefits, technical status, EOSC integration, and sustainability perspective. Outcome-specific summaries of their respective visions are presented at the beginning of each outcome's market analysis in Section: [Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes](#)).

2) Identification and Analysis of Competitors

To identify suitable competitors to analyse for each outcome, we applied a combined approach. First, the vision documents provided selection criteria: once the intended function and value of an outcome were defined, it became possible to determine which platforms perform similar tasks. We then asked each outcome's lead partner to propose the competitors they considered most relevant. To ensure broad coverage, we also selected representative services (e.g., a specific preprint server to represent the wider category). In addition, information from the TRIPLE project was updated and incorporated. After identifying the comparison set per outcome, we applied structured analytical methods. In general, competitor analysis is a method for systematically assessing current and potential competitors within a given sector.

It helps in understanding the competitive environment by examining the strengths, weaknesses, strategies, and positioning of other market actors (Porter, 1980). Typical steps of competitor analyses include:

- identifying direct and indirect competitors
- gathering data on their offerings, target markets, revenue models, and performance
- analysing strategic positioning and unique selling points

Competitor analysis can be conducted through secondary research (e.g., websites, reports, databases), primary research (e.g., interviews, surveys). Initial analysis is usually based on secondary research, while primary research could help deepen our understanding of competitors' further. For LUMEN, the initial analysis was based on secondary research, applied to each identified competitor as described in Section: [Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes](#) under each outcome.

3) Co-Creation (Market Research) Workshops

With the vision and competitor analysis for each outcome, context information and analytical results for each outcome were provided that served as input for the workshops. These workshops applied additional business-modelling methods, including SWOT, PESTLE, gap identification, and unique selling proposition (plus Tetrad analysis for the EOSC Innovation Centre). Each workshop followed the same agenda: 1) Presentation, Discussion and Clarification of Outcome Vision, 2) Presentation of Competitor Analysis Results, 3) SWOT analysis, 4) PESTLE analysis, 5) Gap identification, 6) Unique selling proposition and 7) General Feedback (Tetrad analysis was done in between SWOT and PETSLE for the EOSC Innovation Centre).

In the following, we describe the methods used in the workshops. SWOT, PESTLE, Gap Identification, and Unique Selling Propositions (USP) identification are established tools in business modelling. Tetrad analysis originates from McLuhan's media theory (based on McLuhan, e.g. described for media effects in McLuhan and McLuhan (1988)) and is used in innovation and design research and is also often applied within SSH.

SWOT analysis is a strategic tool used to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of an organisation, project, or initiative. It provides a simple yet structured framework for evaluating both internal capabilities and external conditions and supports sound strategy development (Pickton & Wright, 1998). The method typically involves the following steps:

- Identification of internal strengths and weaknesses, such as resources, expertise, operational efficiency, or gaps in capability
- Identification of external opportunities and threats, based on factors like market trends, technological developments, policy changes, or competitor activity (this can be informed by PESTLE for instance)
- Mapping and analysis of these elements in a 2x2 matrix to highlight strategic priorities
- Synthesis of findings to formulate strategies that leverage strengths, mitigate weaknesses, exploit opportunities, and manage threats (Hill & Westbrook, 1997)

SWOT is often used in combination with other frameworks such as PESTLE to enrich contextual understanding. It can be conducted individually or collaboratively in workshops (Panagiotou, 2003).

PESTLE analysis is a widely used framework for identifying and evaluating external macro-environmental factors that may affect an organisation, project or policy (Aguilar, 1967). The acronym stands for the political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental dimensions. PESTLE analysis is particularly useful in early planning and decision-making processes and helps stakeholders understand the broader context and anticipate future challenges and opportunities (Johnson et al., 2009). The method typically involves a structured process:

- Identification of external factors relevant to the specific context under each PESTLE category.
- Assessment of the potential impact (e.g., positive or negative influence) these factors may have.
- Synthesis of findings to inform strategic planning, risk assessment, or scenario development.

PESTLE analysis can be conducted using a mix of desk research, expert interviews, and workshops. It is often combined with complementary tools such as SWOT analysis to deepen insights (Yüksel, 2012).

Tetrad analysis is a simple framework (based on McLuhan, e.g. described for media effects in McLuhan and McLuhan (1988)) for examining how an initiative, technology, or organisational change affects its wider environment. It considers four lenses:

- Enhance: what the initiative strengthens or increases.
- Retrieve: what older practices, values, or functions it brings back.
- Obsolesce: what it diminishes or makes less central.
- Reverse: what unintended effects may emerge if its influence grows too strong.

By mapping these dimensions, the method helps identify broader patterns of change, anticipate side effects, and support strategic reflection.

Gap identification is a straightforward analytical method used to capture where a concept, service, or system may require further development (Watkins et al., 2012). It typically involves listing relevant thematic areas, describing observed shortcomings or missing elements, and documenting the source of these insights. By structuring observations in this way, the method helps clarify differences between the current state and the desired state and supports subsequent prioritisation of improvements.

Formulating **Unique Selling Propositions (USPs)** is used to clarify what distinguishes a concept, product, or service from existing alternatives. It involves identifying the specific characteristics that add value, create differentiation, or offer an advantage compared to competing solutions. By articulating these distinguishing features, the method supports strategic positioning and helps formulate a clear value promise for stakeholders.

All results generated through these workshop methods are presented in the outcome-specific analyses in Section: [Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes](#), where each LUMEN outcome includes its corresponding SWOT, PESTLE, (+ for EOSC IC Tetrad analysis), along with identified gaps, and unique selling propositions.

4) Synthesis

The final step of the methodology brings together the insights generated through the vision development, competitor analysis, and co-creation market research workshops. The purpose of this synthesis is to integrate the foundational understanding of each outcome with the external landscape and the workshop-based validation into a coherent exploitation baseline. This step depends on the completion of all previous phases, as it draws on their combined outputs to form a strategic and contextualised view of the project outcomes.

The synthesis consolidates the vision documents, the structured competitor analyses, and the workshop results—including SWOT, PESTLE, Tetrad analysis (where relevant), gap identification, and unique selling propositions. This integrated perspective enables a refined interpretation of each outcome’s direction, potential value, and positioning within the broader research and innovation ecosystem. Outcome-specific results are presented and synthesized as key take-aways in Section [Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes](#). Further, insights from step 1-3 fed into Defining Preliminary Sustainability Pathways for LUMEN outcomes, as described in the following.

3.2. Methodology for Defining Preliminary Sustainability Pathways

1) Insights from Market Research

The insights from 1) LUMEN Outcome Visions, 2) Competitor Analyses and 3) Co-Creation (Market Research) Workshops were used to inform reflections on sustainability per outcome, highlighting how sustainability models may align with existing practices in comparable initiatives, and which considerations emerged during the Co-Creation (Market Research) Workshops (see Section [Sustainability Perspectives for Project Outcomes](#) for outcome-specific sustainability considerations based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Workshop). These insights also informed the input that was given to participants to discuss and build upon in the IPL Workshop

2) IPL Workshop

The IPL Workshop gathered cross-partner perspectives on potential sustainability models for key LUMEN outcomes and assessed their feasibility. It was held in a hybrid format and documented through a shared Miro whiteboard (see the whiteboard [here](#)). Following a short input session by WP7 leads, which introduced sustainability model types and synthesised insights from the preceding vision, competitor, and market research work, participants engaged in five parallel group discussions. Each group focused on one sustainability pathway:

- Holistic Perspective on All Outcomes (online group)
- OS White-Label Platform (including metrics, AIDA, visualisation, and meta-search)
- LUMIS
- EOSC Innovation Centre
- Federation of Platforms

All groups worked through the same sequence of tasks:

1. **Discussion of Sustainability Models:** exploration of potential models, including perceived advantages and limitations.
2. **Prioritisation of Feasibility:** voting on suggested models and adding further options where needed.

Synthesis: identification of three key takeaways per outcome.

The results of these discussions are presented in Section [IPL Workshop - Discussing Sustainability Pathways](#).

3) Synthesis

Based on the information from 1) Insights from Market Research, and 2) IPL Workshop, we synthesise ideas regarding sustainability models for the different project outcomes in Section [Exploitation activities undertaken so far](#). These initial ideas on sustainability models serve as a starting point for further elaborations regarding long-term sustainability and exploitation.

4. Market analysis for LUMEN outcomes

4.1. LUMEN white label platform

4.1.1. Vision

The White-Label Discovery Platform is designed as a modular, domain-agnostic solution that any scientific community can adapt. While it builds on technologies developed for GoTriple, it is designed for interoperability and reuse across the LUMEN federation and EOSC ecosystem. Building on GoTriple and expanding its indexes to include descriptions of other valuable content, including datasets, semantic artefacts or software code, the White-Label Discovery Platform will support discovering, enriching, semantically filtering, intelligently linking, and reusing domain-relevant research artefacts. After the vision was presented in the workshop, no significant discussion points were raised.

4.1.2. Competitor analysis

The envisioned LUMEN white label platform is unique in its idea to provide a generic software that scientific domains can implement to make their specific research outputs findable. Yet, any such implementation would face the question why users should use it instead of existing and established search platforms. Our analysis of existing search platforms sought to cover a variety of existing platforms, both cross-disciplinary and specific to individual domains. Initial exploration revealed 23

potential competitors, out of which we analysed 15 in detail. The choice for selecting the 15 platforms shown in Table 1 was made based on multiple criteria: First, we asked the lead partner of each outcome to pre-select the most important competitors from their point of view. Second, we sought to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of search platforms, picking individual platforms (e.g, [arXiv.org](https://arxiv.org)) as representatives for a broader category of platforms (preprint servers). Finally, we retrieved and updated information that was available from the prior [TRIPLE project](#) to complement our analysis.

The first relevant distinction is with regard to the focus each platform has. Table 1 lists the analysed competitors along with their core focus.

Table 1: Overview of competitors for LUMEN white label platform

General purpose discovery platforms	Social networks	Biomedical literature	Full-text aggregators / preprint servers	Special document types
Scopus	Academia.edu	PubMed	CORE	Overton.io
Web of Science	ResearchGate	Europe PMC	JSTOR	Lens.org
OpenAlex			arXiv.org	
Semantic Scholar				
Dimensions				
Google Scholar				

The competitors listed in Table 1 further differ with respect to the following dimensions:

- Coverage
 - Geography
 - Language
 - Topic
 - Types of content (journal articles, conferences, books, patents, policy documents, preprints)
- Inclusion criteria
- Simplicity / complexity of user interface
- Access to metadata and/or full-text
- API

- Integration with reference manager software (Zotero, Citavi, custom solutions)
- Social networking features

A comprehensive analysis of all competitors listed above according to (a) their most relevant functions and features, (b) their added value for stakeholders, and (c) their relevance for consideration within LUMEN is provided in [the Annex](#).

4.1.3. SWOT

Table 2: SWOT analysis for LUMEN white label platform

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built with communities based on user needs • Leverages existing GoTriple platform experience • EOSC open source solution potentially applicable to every discipline • Easy onboarding for data providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balance between tailoring to community needs and enabling cross-domain interaction • Wide range of involved communities, diverse research fields and methodologies • Cannot filter bad metadata effectively • Ongoing support and upgrade needs • Too long production timeline compared to market speed
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services for data providers to improve data quality • AI integration for both user service and metadata curation • General political climate supporting sovereignty in infrastructure • Dataset search capabilities as potential USP • Tie into the movement on research assessment and the valorisation of multilingualism (given that the platform aims to be multilingual) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong competition from existing broader solutions with established market presence • Harvesting "alternative content" (non-publications) is challenging • Connecting to EOSC core services might be challenging • Search engines might become outdated compared to AI chatbots, due to the evolution of discovery practices

We note that the points presented in Table 2 reflect the input given by our workshop participants. On further reflection, some of the aspects listed under "weaknesses"

can also be understood as strengths, such as the wide range of communities involved in the project. Further work on the white label platform will take into account how to manage the tension between the involvement of diverse communities as both a potential weakness but also an inherent strength.

4.1.4. PESTLE

Table 3: PESTLE analysis for LUMEN white label platform

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policies supporting open science and digital sovereignty • Defense priorities potentially affecting research funding
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding challenges for infrastructure and long-term sustainability • Economic models changing may influence science • Competition from commercial platforms
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General hesitance to use new tools • Need for AI literacy • Different communities requiring formation alongside platform development
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological maturity questions • EU-centricness as potential advantage • Competition from various initiatives in the EOSC context building data sharing platforms
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU AI Act implications • Data Act and Data Governance Act compliance • Regulations on data sharing
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data carbon footprint concerns with increasing data volume and user demand

4.1.5. Functional Requirements & Gaps

The workshop identified the following critical needs:

- Alignment between different communities
- Technical integration with EOSC core services
- Balance between customisation and standardisation

4.1.6. Unique selling proposition

Discussion on the platform's USP led to the following points:

- The focus on multilingualism as a key differentiator
- The ability to search for datasets
- The platform's availability to other domains as a general purpose search platform

4.1.7. Key takeaways

The following key takeaways can be derived from the work undertaken so far:

- **Open Source Priority:** Strong consensus on prioritising open source solutions aligns with EOSC principles and ensures sustainability and community ownership.
- **Cross-Domain Balance Challenge:** The tension between domain-specific customisation and cross-domain interoperability emerged as a critical design challenge requiring careful navigation.
- **Sustainability Concerns:** All LUMEN outcomes face significant ongoing support and maintenance challenges, necessitating sustainable business models beyond project funding. This therefore also applies to the white label platform.
- **Community-Driven Development:** Success depends on deep community engagement, but coordinating diverse disciplinary needs while maintaining coherent platforms poses significant challenges.

4.2. Federation of platforms

4.2.1. Vision

The Federation of Platforms connects discovery platforms across Social Sciences & Humanities, Mathematics, Earth System Science, and Molecular Dynamics, using LUMEN's Data Mesh framework to enable cross-domain discovery while preserving domain sovereignty. Each community maintains data ownership, adhering to shared standards via Data Contracts that define structure, format, and terms of use. Currently, the ecosystem includes GoTriple (SSH) and two Mathematics platforms (Centre Mersenne, zbMATH Open), with new platforms for Earth System Science and Molecular Dynamics being developed and ongoing development on GoTriple and Centre Mersenne.

Key discussion points in the workshop included:

- **Target Audience Clarification:** Participants clarified that the primary target audience is not end users but infrastructure providers and research communities. This distinction is important for understanding the federation's role as an enabling technology rather than a direct service platform, since the federation will enable cooperation and data exchange between domain-specific discovery platforms, without providing user-facing front-ends.
- **Technical Architecture Understanding:** Reference was made to deliverable D4.1, which provides detailed technical architecture specifications. Participants noted that while the vision remains consistent, the technical documentation adds significant detail about implementation.
- **Interdisciplinary Potential:** Questions arose about connections between seemingly disparate fields (e.g., SSH and molecular dynamics), highlighting both the challenge and opportunity of creating meaningful cross-domain linkages.
- **Governance Timing Concerns:** Participants observed that technical architecture development precedes governance structures in the project timeline, creating potential risks of misalignment between technical capabilities and community needs.

4.2.2. Competitor analysis

Initial competitor analysis for the federation of platforms identified 17 potential competitors. We eventually selected seven competitors for in-depth analysis (Table 4). We first asked the lead partner for the federation of platforms to pre-select the most relevant platforms. The final choice for selecting the seven platforms was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of federated platforms for data exchange. For the purpose of the analysis, the seven platforms were grouped into four conceptual groups (see Table 4).

Table 4: Overview of competitors for the Federation of Platforms

Frameworks	Examples of federated data portals	Commercial solutions	Political / strategic visions
Open Data Mesh Platform	CESSDA	Dawex Data Exchange (Data Hub, Data Space, Data Marketplace)	Gaia-X
International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) - Reference Architecture	EPOS (European Plate Observing System) - Dataportal		

	Open Science Data Federation (OSDF)
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Key aspects of the IDSA and Gaia-X which were identified included the following:

- **International Data Space Association**
 - Standardized architecture (IDS-RAM) for secure and sovereign data exchange;
 - Provides certified components like Connectors, Brokers, Identity Providers.
 - ⇒ provides a technical standard and framework
- **Gaia-X**
 - Political-Strategic Initiative, providing a vision for an ecosystem
 - Its mission: “Creating the de facto standard to enable federated and trusted data and infrastructure ecosystems, by developing a set of specifications, rules, policies, and a verification framework”

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) functions as an umbrella organisation for individual data archives. It provides tools, such as a Data Catalogue, Vocabulary Service, Metadata Validator, as well as training on “how to discover, use, manage and preserve research data”. Data can be accessed via <http://datacatalogue.cessda.eu>.

Similarly, the European Plate Observing System (EPOS) is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure that facilitates the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community in Europe. It provides a federated data infrastructure connecting European research infrastructures, with interactive map, a catalogue, and download services.

4.2.3. SWOT

Table 5: SWOT analysis for the Federation of Platforms

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community-driven governance model: Unlike top-down approaches (Gaia-X, IDS), LUMEN is research-centric and aligned with open science principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Complex onboarding: Architecture may appear too abstract for communities with limited experience in FAIR practices

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Value preservation: The framework ensures "value stays where the knowledge is," maintaining community autonomy ● Bridge between approaches: LUMEN integrates bottom-up scientific federations with FAIR-by-design data mesh principles ● JUST Data annotation framework: Integration of ethical data practices beyond technical FAIR compliance ● Trust and quality focus: Emphasis on metadata quality to ensure data discoverability and reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community dependence: High reliance on continuous community engagement could slow progress ● Broad scope challenges: Supporting multiple research communities increases coordination and resource demands ● Governance complexity: Despite bottom-up intentions, governance structure appears complex ● Tool coordination: A diverse toolset offers flexibility but requires active coordination to ensure interoperability
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Catalysing cross-domain scientific uses: Potential for novel interdisciplinary research ● EOSC alignment: Strong integration opportunities with EOSC ● JUST Data framework development: Opportunity to establish new research standards ● Interdisciplinary demonstrations: Development of use cases that showcase cross-domain collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Delayed value perception: Cross-domain benefits may be difficult to identify before metadata alignment ● Community engagement timing: Risk of developing disconnected solutions without early community involvement ● Competition from large-scale initiatives: Potential overlap with initiatives such as Gaia-X, IDS ● Technology maintenance: Continuous updates required to ensure reliable data access ● Traditional resistance: Some scientific communities may be hesitant to adopt new platforms ● Large scope risks: Broad target audiences may lead to diluted focus and coordination challenges

4.2.4. PESTLE

Table 6: PESTLE analysis for Federation of Platforms

Category	Key Points
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<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alignment with the European data strategy provides opportunities ● Integration with the EOSC governance model is necessary ● Centralisation of EU science policy creates new opportunities ● Digital sovereignty concerns support community-driven approaches
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● National and EU funding dependencies affect long-term sustainability ● Long-term funding is needed beyond the project lifecycle ● Innovation potential may support economic growth ● Funding availability varies across countries and institutions
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Diverse academic cultures require flexibility and adaptation ● Communities expect transparency in governance processes ● Digital literacy and multilingual access remain important needs ● Expectations for inclusivity in science are growing
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alignment across communities presents ongoing challenges ● Flexibility must be balanced with interoperability standards ● Compliance with the AI Act, Data Act, and Data Governance Act is required ● Scalable infrastructure is needed
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GDPR and data protection compliance is essential ● Copyright and licensing present complexity for scholarly content ● Data contracts help clarify conditions for sharing and reuse ● Cross-border data sharing agreements are required
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Distributed architectures have an unclear carbon footprint ● There is growing demand for energy-efficient digital infrastructure ● Federated approaches may be more environmentally friendly than centralized ones ● Sustainability metrics are needed to evaluate environmental impact

4.2.5. Functional Requirements & Gaps

Critical gaps identified include:

- **Community engagement mechanisms:** Unclear pathways for involving communities in development and governance
- **Sustainable business model:** Undefined sustainability approach post-project
- **Integration clarity:** Uncertain EOSC integration levels and ongoing changes

4.2.6. Unique Selling Proposition

Based on the workshop, we identified the following USPs of the Federation of Platforms:

- **Bottom-up, community-sovereign approach** unique in European research landscape
- **FAIR-by-design data mesh** specifically for scientific communities
- **Operational governance**, not just architecture
- **Researcher-to-researcher** focus
- **Scalable design** for new community integration
- **Lower data carbon footprint** when implemented properly
- **Trust through community ownership** and quality standards

4.2.7. Key Takeaways

The following key takeaways can be derived from the work undertaken so far:

- **Community engagement must begin immediately** - The risk of developing disconnected solutions is too high to delay community involvement until later project stages
- **Governance and technology must co-evolve** - The current sequential approach (tech first, governance later) poses alignment risks
- **The federation's unique position requires careful messaging** - LUMEN bridges multiple existing approaches, which is both its strength and a communication challenge
- **Sustainability planning cannot wait** - With dependencies on external funding and evolving EOSC landscape, sustainability strategies need immediate attention
- **Cross-domain value must be demonstrated early** - Use cases showing interdisciplinary benefits are essential for maintaining engagement across diverse communities.

4.3. LUMIS

4.3.1. Vision

LUMIS aims at providing an integrated environment for building and testing semantic artefacts (controlled vocabularies, thesauri, ontologies,...), by seamlessly connecting multiple existing open source tools in one platform. This working space addresses the needs of knowledge experts and ontologists.

Advantages of LUMIS include:

- **Integration of Tools:** Unlike existing solutions, the space aims to connect multiple tools, allowing for more efficient workflows for ontology creation and testing.
- **Ontology Testing:** It enables testing ontologies with actual data, providing feedback that can refine the initial creation. This feature, including methodologies for ensuring FAIR compliance, is not readily available in current tools.
- **Early Concept Check:** The space allows users to check if a concept already exists in other ontologies during the creation phase, reducing time and effort compared to the current post-creation check.

The workshop participants refined the vision for the FAIR Semantic Management Space, emphasising several critical aspects:

- **Lifecycle Support:** The platform should support the complete lifecycle of semantic artifacts, not just organisation and management, but also creation and systematic processes
- **Tool Orchestration:** Rather than creating new tools, the focus is on orchestrating existing tools to enable seamless workflows and transitions between them
- **Target Audience:** The platform is explicitly designed for ontology experts and knowledge engineers, not general users, though general users will benefit indirectly from the ontologies created
- **Methodology Integration:** The platform will build on established methodologies like LOT (Linked Open Terms) methodology.

4.3.2. Competitor analysis

Competitor analysis identified 22 potential competitors, and analysed 15 in-depth. The full list of competitors analysed in-depth included: Protege, BioPortal, Metaphactory, Centree, Pollparty Semantic Suite, Graphology, OntoME, Palantir Ontology Manager, TopBraid EDG, Zazuko Ontology Manager, Graphite, Kaiasm OntoKai, Laces Ontology, Manager, Intelligent Taxonomy Manager, Datavid Ontology Management. The choice for selecting the 15 competitors for in-depth analysis was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different services for managing semantic artefacts, and informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

Analysis highlighted the following key features of existing solutions to managing semantic artefacts:

- **Ontology/Taxonomy Management**
 - Tools to create, edit, align, and manage ontologies or taxonomies using standards like OWL, SKOS. Essential for building semantic structures.
 - *Platforms:* Protege, Metaphactory, Centree, PoolParty, Graphologi, TopBraid EDG, Graphite, Laces, Mondeca, Datavid
- **Collaborative Editing & Governance**
 - Support for multiple users to work together, often with roles, workflows, versioning, approvals, and discussion tools. Key for scalable knowledge work.
 - *Platforms:* Protege, Metaphactory, Centree, PoolParty, Graphologi, OntoME, Zazuko, Mondeca
- **AI-Assisted Suggestions / Automation**
 - Use of AI for tasks like auto-classification, concept suggestions, mapping assistance, ontology alignment. Boosts efficiency and scalability.
 - *Platforms:* Protege, Metaphactory, Centree, PoolParty, TopBraid EDG, Graphologi, Mondeca
- **Visualisation (Graph, Tree, etc.)**
 - Graphical display of ontology/taxonomy structures (e.g., trees, graphs), helpful for users to understand and explore models.
 - *Platforms:* Protege, BioPortal, Metaphactory, PoolParty, Graphologi, TopBraid EDG, Mondeca
- **FAIR/Data Catalog Integration**
 - Ability to connect with data catalogs and support FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Important for data ecosystems.
 - *Platforms:* Metaphactory, TopBraid EDG (Others may allow it indirectly)
- **Quality Control / Governance / Audit Trail**
 - Features for validation, consistency checks, audit trails, version history, user permissions – ensures model integrity.
 - *Platforms:* Centree, PoolParty, Graphologi, TopBraid EDG, Mondeca, Zazuko
- **Standards Support (OWL, SKOS, SHACL, etc.)**
 - Enables interoperability and reuse by following formal specifications (e.g., OWL for ontologies, SKOS for taxonomies, SHACL for constraints).
 - *Platforms:* Protege, Metaphactory, Centree, PoolParty, Graphologi, TopBraid EDG, OntoME, Mondeca
- **API Integration / Extensibility**

- Allows tools to be embedded in workflows or connected to other systems, often via APIs or SDKs.
 - *Platforms:* BioPortal, Metaphactory, Centree, PoolParty, Graphologi, TopBraid EDG

4.3.3. SWOT

Table 7: SWOT analysis for LUMIS

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Expert Resources: Strong availability of ontology and graph experts within the project ● Development Approach: Lean development methodology (MVP) with a dedicated, mixed-expertise team ● Clear Roadmap: Prioritized backlog under construction with known experts for community engagement ● LUMEN Integration: Teams of potential users already working within the LUMEN ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resource Constraints: Many ambitious goals but limited team size ● Technical Maturity: Platform doesn't exist yet (TRL 1-2), though component tools are established ● User Base Limitations: Designed for experts only, potentially limiting adoption ● Communication Challenges: Siloed effects between work packages affecting cross-WP understanding ● Sustainability Concerns: Difficulty and cost of maintenance after project end
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Market Position: Unique offering that fills a gap in the EOSC Federation service portfolio ● Strategic Alignment: Strong connection to EU Open Data policies and e-government initiatives ● Knowledge Leverage: Ability to capitalize on accumulated knowledge from other EU projects ● Collaboration Potential: Partnership opportunities with existing tool providers ● Cross-Domain Application: Domain-independent design enabling broad applicability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● External Dependencies: Reliance on externally developed tools requiring continuous alignment ● Adoption Risk: Potential lack of community adoption ● Change Management: Brand loyalty and user habits creating resistance to behavior change ● Technical Risks: New releases of integrated tools potentially causing compatibility issues

4.3.4. PESTLE

Table 8: PESTLE analysis for LUMIS

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong alignment with EC digital strategy and digital sovereignty initiatives • Supports implementation of open science policies and FAIR principles • Potential participation across European countries favors scalability
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical need for sustainable business model to cover server and maintenance costs • Anticipated budget reductions in next Framework program pose risks • Opportunity to leverage EOSC Federation Node for infrastructure cost reduction • Large AI investments creating favorable funding environment
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge of onboarding users lacking ontology development expertise • Need identified for semantics across many communities • Opportunity to enhance digital equity through improved access
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current immaturity of interoperability standards in EOSC landscape • Emergence of neurosymbolic AI and Graph-AI integration (GraphRAG) • All currently considered tools are open source
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDPR compliance requirements for user data management • Need to ensure data deletion capabilities across connected tools
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Server energy use and alignment with green IT practices • Option to mitigate through self-hosting or EOSC node integration

4.3.5. Functional Requirements & Gaps

The workshop identified the following critical gaps:

- **Tool Integration Architecture:** at the time of the workshop (June 2025), critical decisions were pending on which tools to integrate and communication protocols with providers
- **Cross-Domain Application:** Unclear how the platform will serve multiple scientific domains effectively

- **User Experience:** Platform appears abstract for generic users despite expert focus
- **Internal Capacity:** Gap between ambitious objectives and available team resources

4.3.6. Unique selling proposition

Based on the workshop, we identified the following USPs of LUMIS:

- **Comprehensive Integration:** Only solution integrating multiple semantic tools into unified workflow
- **FAIR-by-Design:** Implements FAIR principles from the start
- **EOSC Enablement:** Specifically addresses semantic interoperability gap in EOSC
- **AI Enhancement:** Incorporates advanced AI for automation and assistance.

4.3.7. Key Takeaways

The following key takeaways can be derived from the work undertaken so far:

- **Clear Market Need:** Strong demand exists for integrated semantic artifact management, addressing current tool fragmentation
- **Expert-Focused Design:** Deliberate choice to target ontology experts rather than general users, with clear understanding of limitations
- **Sustainability Challenge:** Critical need to develop viable business model for post-project maintenance
- **Technical Dependencies:** Success heavily dependent on external tool stability and continued development
- **EOSC Strategic Fit:** LUMIS fills identified gaps in EOSC semantic interoperability services.

4.4. AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA)

4.4.1. Vision

The AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) transforms research discovery from keyword searches to natural language conversations, directly answering researchers' specific questions based on scientific literature. AIDA will integrate the White-Label Discovery Platform, allowing a seamless process from content discovery to AI-assisted analysis and conversation. After the vision was presented in the workshop, no significant discussion points were raised.

4.4.2. Competitor analysis

There are many existing solutions for AI-assisted research discovery, and given the pace of development around LLMs, this abundance of tools can only be expected to increase. Our analysis identified 17 potential competitors (as of May 2025), and analysed seven in-depth. The choice for selecting the seven AI-tools was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of AI assisted ways for knowledge discovery, and informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

Table 9: Overview of competitors for AIDA

Chatbot search	PDF interrogation
Consensus	NotebookLM
Scite	SciSpace
Elicit	
SciSpace	
IrisAI	

As outlined in Table 9, The analysed tools can be grouped into two types of services:

1. Chatbots with a query bar that search the literature, providing researchers with answers and references
2. Tools that researchers to interrogate/chat with one or more PDFs

The first category of chatbots commonly enables:

- Search via natural language
- Summarisation of retrieved literature
- Categorisation and filtering of search results (supporting vs. contradicting, articles types, sample size, etc.)

Analysed exemplary services in this domain are Consensus, Scite, Elicit, SciSpace, and IrisAI.

In contrast, tools such as NotebookLM or SciSpace enable users to directly chat with the chatbot about individual documents that were uploaded to a work-space, enabling in-depth conversations based on specific sources.

Both approaches seem meaningful for enabling next-generation research discovery.

On the technical side, the analysed services use a mix of GPT-based custom or third-party **models**, such as ChatGPT, Claude, or Gemini. **Retrieval** of sources is implemented through various combinations of approaches, but there is a strong focus on Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG). **Data sources** primarily are found from openly available services offering an API, such as OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar, or Crossref.

4.4.3. SWOT

Table 10: SWOT analysis for AIDA

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to scientific publication content through LLM ● Trusted sources approach ● LLM as default search approach aligns with current trends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need to mitigate against hallucinations ● Cross-domain or out-of-context queries pose challenges ● Server costs and model costs ● Hard to identify key selling points compared to competitors
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evolution from outdated search engines to AI chatbots ● Create context-driven service ● Science-based output focus ● Cross-reference with knowledge documentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● User expectations may not be manageable ● AI biases including hallucinations and citation issues ● Competing against big corporations ● Fast development of technology

4.4.4. PESTLE

Table 11: PESTLE analysis for AIDA

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU policies supporting open science and digital sovereignty ● National interest in AI and data centres ● Defense priorities potentially affecting research funding ● EU interest in trusted AI applications
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Funding challenges for infrastructure and long-term

	<p>sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Economic models changing may influence science ● Competition from commercial platforms
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● General hesitance to use new tools ● Users increasingly accustomed to AI for finding responses ● Need for AI literacy ● Different communities requiring formation alongside platform development
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Constant development in LLMs necessitating updates ● Technological maturity questions ● EU-centricness as potential advantage ● Gap to US and China in AI technology
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EU AI Act implications ● Data Act and Data Governance Act compliance ● Regulations on data sharing ● GDPR considerations
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data carbon footprint concerns ● Sustainability of server infrastructure ● Alignment with green IT practices

4.4.5. Functional Requirements & Gaps

The workshop identified the following key functional requirements:

- Clear focus differentiation from other chatbot integrations,
- Mitigation of hallucinations
- Cross-domain query handling

4.4.6. Unique Selling Proposition

During the workshop the following unique selling proposition was formulated. AIDA...

- enables natural-language search across domain-specific data sources,
- provides reliable knowledge references to support accurate results,
- delivers effective data retrieval through well-managed annotations.

4.4.7. Key Takeaways

- **Open Source Priority:** Strong consensus on prioritising open source solutions aligns with EOSC principles and ensures sustainability and community ownership.
- **Cross-Domain Balance Challenge:** The tension between domain-specific customisation and cross-domain interoperability emerged as a critical design challenge requiring careful navigation.
- **AI Integration as Differentiator:** While AI/LLM integration presents opportunities, concerns about hallucinations, biases, and rapidly changing technology require robust mitigation strategies.
- **Sustainability Concerns:** All outcomes face significant ongoing support and maintenance challenges, necessitating sustainable business models beyond project funding.
- **Community-Driven Development:** Success depends on deep community engagement, but coordinating diverse disciplinary needs while maintaining coherent platforms poses significant challenges.

4.5. Interdisciplinary Meta-Search-Service

4.5.1. Vision

The initial formulation of the vision for the interdisciplinary meta-search service was as follows:

The LUMEN Interdisciplinary Meta-Search Service enables cross-domain research by providing unified access to content from federated communities. Built on GoTriple, it features a multilingual search engine with advanced functionalities like visualisation and Boolean operators, and a recommendation engine for interdisciplinary suggestions.

During the workshops, participants discussed this statement and highlighted the following points:

- **Scope Clarity:** There was uncertainty about what exactly would be shared via the meta-search service and how it would relate to existing search functionalities within individual platforms.
- **Integration Approach:** An open question is whether the meta-search would become the default search approach for the discovery platforms or operate as an overlay service.

- **Value Proposition:** Participants stressed the importance of highlighting the added benefits of the meta-search service beyond what existing solutions offer.
- **Technical Alignment:** Concerns were raised about the substantial work needed to align discovery platforms semantically (e.g., defining what constitutes a "dataset").

4.5.2. Competitor analysis

Many services exist that offer search functionalities across domains. For most large search platforms (OpenAlex, Scopus, Google Scholar), this is the default approach. Our competitor analysis identified 15 close competitors, and analysed eight in-depth:

- BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine)
- CORE
- Google Scholar
- OpenAlex
- OpenAIRE Explore
- Dimensions
- Semantic Scholar
- The Lens

The choice for selecting the eight competitors on interdisciplinary search was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of search platforms enabling cross-disciplinary knowledge discovery, and informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

Table 12 compares them according to selected key features.

Table 12: Key competitors for the interdisciplinary meta-search service and their features

Platform	Academic Resource Aggregation	Advanced Search & Filters	Semantic Enrichment / Graph	Personalized Recommendations	Interdisciplinary Coverage	API / Integration Support	Free to Use / Open Access
BASE	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
CORE	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Google Scholar	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
OpenAlex	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

OpenAIRE Explore	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Dimensions	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗ (Subscription)
Semantic Scholar	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
The Lens	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ / Optional Paid API

Beyond the core features outlined in the table, our analysis also shows that existing solutions offer some or all of the following functionalities:

- **Autocomplete:** Suggests terms as users type to speed up discovery.
 - Available with BASE, Google Scholar, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE Explore, Semantic Scholar, The Lens
- **Citation-Based Recommendations:** Uses citation data (e.g., "Cited by", "Related articles") to suggest content.
 - Available with Google Scholar, OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar, The Lens
- **Semantic Filtering / Concept-Based Search:** Allows filtering and grouping results by topics, entities, or concepts beyond basic keywords.
 - Available with OpenAlex, Semantic Scholar, The Lens
- **Faceted Filtering:** Offers structured filters like publication type, access rights, discipline, etc.
 - Available with BASE, CORE, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE Explore, Dimensions, The Lens
- **Browser-Based Tools / Plugins:** Supports recommendation or search via browser extensions.
 - Available with BASE and CORE

4.5.3. SWOT

Table 13: SWOT analysis for the interdisciplinary meta-search service

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-domain Capability: True cross-resource discovery across federated, multilingual, and semantically aligned platforms - a capability no current competitor offers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Unclear Scope: Ambiguity about whether search should be integrated with existing platform searches

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Novel Technical Approach: Integration of sovereignty and federated search represents an innovative solution ● Multilingual Support: Advanced multilingual approach to searching that aims at solving metadata challenges across languages ● Community Ownership: Emphasis on community-driven ownership model ● Prepared Use Cases: Having developed use cases for cross-domain results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Metadata Quality: Standards and processes for metadata not strict or well-communicated enough ● UX Challenges: Difficulty in designing an interface that enables federated search in a meaningful and accessible way ● Technical Dependencies: High dependency on community metadata quality and alignment
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strategic Positioning: Position LUMEN as the EOSC-wide gateway for interdisciplinary research, especially in emerging fields ● Ambassador Program: Find and engage researchers who already work cross-domains ● Growing Interdisciplinarity: Increasing trend toward interdisciplinary research could create natural demand ● Unique Features: Recovery of datasets in relation to papers offers a unique asset ● EOSC Integration: Sustainability through deep integration with EOSC infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong Competition: Established competitors like OpenAlex or OpenAIRE Explore already serve similar functions ● User Resistance/Adoption Barriers: Typical resistance to adopting new services without clear quality improvements ● Metadata Challenges: Risk of poor metadata quality or lack of standardisation undermining effectiveness ● Weak Differentiation: Unclear unique selling proposition compared to comprehensive existing solutions

4.5.4. PESTLE

Table 14: PESTLE analysis for the interdisciplinary meta-search service

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● European open science strategies and EOSC mandates support LUMEN's federated, non-commercial positioning ● Development of EOSC federation presents both opportunities and complexity
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sustainability model needed beyond project funding through the

	<p>EOSC Innovation Centre</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding instability for infrastructure threatens long-term maintenance • Need for diverse funding strategy including institutional partners, not only EC funding
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing expectations for sophisticated search capabilities driven by modern search engines and LLMs • Multilingualism increasingly important for inclusivity • Significant training/education needs to help users understand meta-service value • Barriers in getting non-technical users to adopt technical solutions
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability depends critically on standardized APIs and shared semantics • Risk of semantic misalignment if communities expose metadata with low granularity • Lightweight federation approach avoids centralisation overhead
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-border metadata aggregation must comply with GDPR • Data ownership and licensing constraints need careful navigation
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightweight federated approach contributes to sustainability goals

4.5.5. Functional Requirements & Gaps

The workshop identified the following critical gaps:

- Lack of clear, compelling use cases for cross-domain search (yet)
- Unclear differentiation between white label platform search and meta-search functionality
- Missing clarity on interdisciplinary cross-connections implementation
- Need for well-designed UX/UI that doesn't overwhelm users with complexity

4.5.6. Unique selling proposition

The current vision of the meta-search service has the following USPs:

- Enabling serendipitous discovery through cross-domain metadata connections
- Specifically designed for interdisciplinary research purposes
- Community-driven ownership model
- No commercial interests, ensuring unbiased results
- Unique capability to link datasets with publications across domains

- True semantic enrichment beyond simple aggregation

4.5.7. Key Takeaways

The following key takeaways can be derived from the work undertaken so far:

- **Differentiation must be clear:** The service needs a compelling answer to "why use this instead of existing solutions?" that goes beyond technical features.
- **Metadata quality is foundational:** Without robust metadata standards and quality assurance, the entire service risks failure.
- **Early adopters are key:** Focus on researchers already working cross-domain as ambassadors and early users.
- **Simplicity in complexity:** The interface must make complex federated searching feel simple and intuitive.

4.6. Metrics Service

4.6.1. Vision

The Metrics Service aims to provide transparent, domain-relevant usage and citation metrics aligned with Open Science principles, specifically supporting early-career researchers and adhering to CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) principles. It would serve two main purposes:

- Enable scientists to assess search results
- Enable scientometric reports for administrators of Research Performing Organisations

After the vision was presented in the workshop, no significant discussion points were raised.

4.6.2. Competitor analysis

Many services exist that offer metrics on scholarly content to users. Our competitor analysis identified 10 close competitors, and analysed four in-depth:

- OpenAlex
- Web of Science / InCites
- Scopus / SciVal
- Dimensions

The choice for selecting the four competitors on metrics was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of metric providers, and

informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

Table 15 compares them according to selected key features.

Table 15: Key competitors for the metrics service and their features

Metrics / Platform	OpenAlex	WoS/InCites	Scopus / SciVal	Dimensions
Total citation count	✓	✓	✓	✓
Field-weighted citation impact	✗	✗	✓	✓
Category/Journal Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI/JNCI)	✗	✓	✗	✗
Relative Citation Ratio (RCR)	✗	✗	✗	✓
Field Citation Ratio (FCR)	✗	✗	✗	✓
Impact relative to world average	✗	✓	✗	✗
H-index (with and without self-citations)	✓	✓	✓	✗
Citation impact over time (e.g., cumulative per year)	✗	✓	✗	✗
Number of citing countries	✗	✗	✓	✗

Our analysis further highlighted the following features as being relevant for LUMEN:

- APIs and Integration, offering access to the underlying data for more advanced use cases.
- Linking of metadata, either through semantic similarity or citation networks
- Rankings based on various relevance and citation indicators, including field- or journal-normalized metrics.
- Tools for monitoring and evaluation, such as tracking of citation trends or institutional benchmarks.

4.6.3. SWOT

Table 16: SWOT analysis for the metrics service

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support for early careers ● Built with/for communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Different domains have different metrics needs ● Metrics are expected on nearly every platform - unclear USP ● Ongoing support and upgrade needs
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create metrics in line with CoARA principles ● Link with research assessment reform movement ● Development of incentive models for dataset maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk of using metrics that boost established careers only ● Strong competitors ● Different metrics standards/needs across disciplines

4.6.4. PESTLE

Table 17: PESTLE analysis for the metrics service

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Can tie in with ongoing agenda of reform of research assessment
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competition from commercial platforms
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hesitancy to new metrics - users might expect certain established metrics
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dependency on technical infrastructure (PIDs)
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need to ensure alignment with EU policies on responsible assessment
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potential for sustainability / data carbon footprint metrics?

4.6.5. Conclusions

A core tension in the design of the metrics is to find the right mix among three dimensions, providing metrics aligned with

- ongoing initiatives towards reforming research assessment and responsible use of metrics (CoARA)
- disciplinary needs which might differ
- User expectations towards established metrics

4.7. Advanced Visualisation Tools

4.7.1. Vision

These LUMEN visualisation tools aim to enhance content discovery through intuitive visual interfaces, providing clear representations of search results, knowledge elements, and relationships between research outputs. After the vision was presented in the workshop, no significant discussion points were raised.

4.7.2. Competitor analysis

There are many available services for visualising results of searches across academic databases. Our competitor analysis identified 16 close competitors, and analysed six in-depth:

- Lens.org
- ResearchRabbit
- Nomic ATLAS
- Connected Papers
- VOSviewer
- OpenKnowledge Maps
- Inciteful.xyz

The choice for selecting the six competitors on visualising search results in knowledge discovery platforms was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different types of visualisation approaches, and informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

The most common feature of the analysed visualisation tools is to display relationships between papers, concepts, or authors using citation, co-authorship, or similarity links. This feature is present in all the six analysed competitors. Figure 1 shows an example of such a visualisation using VOSviewer.

Figure 1: Network visualisation with VOSviewer

Another common feature is to visualise nodes such as papers along a timeline, such as in Figure 2. As can be seen from the figure, some tools allow the user to zoom, filter, and explore large knowledge graphs based on further (potentially custom) criteria.

Further features include visualisations of semantic similarity (based on NLP methods such as embeddings) and options for saving, sharing, and reloading of graph-based research maps.

Figure 2: Example of timeline view from ResearchRabbit

4.7.3. SWOT

Table 18: SWOT analysis for the advanced visualisation tools

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contribution of specific domains in design ● Already some visualisation in GoTriple to build upon ● Cross-domain visualisation capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need to investigate visualisation needs by specific domains ● Open questions about what data to visualize where ● Danger of UI overcomplexity ● Ongoing support and upgrade needs
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Real added value for users through information mapping ● Lot of open source APIs available ● Possible partnership with GRAPHIA project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adapting to changing visualisation APIs and models ● Risk of developing too big with technology change risk ● Unclear understanding of added value from communities

4.7.4. PESTLE

Table 19: PESTLE analysis for the advanced visualisation tools

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The advanced visualisation tools could become a bridge with decision makers → a way to visualise results to gain their interest
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developments by commercial service providers
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General hesitance to use new tools • Advanced visualisation is interpretation of data, is this an issue for research? • Possibility to gain time → make research faster and easier by visualising aggregated results
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced viz needs lot of work on underlying infrastructure / data quality
<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crossreference with the Legal Ontology of IP Rights
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with green IT practices

4.7.5. Conclusions

The competitor analysis identified a range of existing tools - offering visualisation tools that match or go beyond existing solutions is difficult. The workshops identified a need to better understand domain-specific visualisation needs and to avoid UI overcomplexity. Regarding the core value proposition, participants discussed the potential for multi-domain representations and IP/attribution tracking

4.8. EOSC Innovation Centre

4.8.1. Vision

The EOSC Innovation Centre - envisioned as a sustainable legacy of LUMEN - will support new ways of conducting and thinking about research and the interface to other domains. Its vision is still evolving. Initially drafted as a centre for technology transfer, business models, and exploitation pathways for use cases and new projects enabled by LUMEN, the aim has been refined and refocused during multiple workshops. The current vision can be summarised as follows:

The function of the EOSC Innovation Centre is to be primarily about innovation in research and its application by open scientific domains connecting through the affordances of technologies and interdisciplinary meetings.

The methodology for its development combines desk research, hands-on engagement with industry and stakeholders in IPLs, and interviews with ecosystem participants. Questions on its organisational form and day-to-day operations remain open at this point.

Launching near the project's end, it aims to foster interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange, ensuring long-term impact and innovation beyond LUMEN.

4.8.2. Competitor analysis

The competitive landscape reveals no direct competitors for the specific vision of the EOSC innovation centre. Out of an initial list of six competitors, we analysed five in detail:

- Atos
- Fraunhofer Innovation Clusters
- European Digital Innovation Hubs
- EOSC Digital Innovation Hub
- OPERAS Innovation Lab

The choice for selecting the five competitors on innovation centres was made in order to provide comprehensive coverage across different approaches towards innovation labs, and informed by a pre-selection of relevant competitors made by the outcome lead partner.

While European Digital Innovation Hubs focus on SME digitalisation, OPERAS Innovation Lab serves SSH specifically, and industrial innovation centres pursue product development, none address cross-domain research innovation as proposed. This represents both an opportunity (unique positioning) and a challenge (no proven model to follow).

4.8.3. SWOT

Table 20: SWOT analysis for the EOSC Innovation Centre

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EOSC Integration: LUMEN's existing position within EOSC facilitates landscape understanding and partnership development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Clarity Deficit: Fundamental uncertainty about "what it does" and specific use cases ● Sustainability Model: Unclear funding pathways and long-term viability

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Foundation: The LUMEN Data Mesh framework provides solid architectural foundation for distributed, community-driven initiatives ● Cross-domain Expertise: Proven capability in building bridges across heterogeneous contexts ● Existing Tools: Software and white-label services under development can support ongoing innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus Issues: Risk of being overly ambitious without clear prioritisation ● Late Launch Risk: Proposed launch near project end increases failure risk
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SSH Data Space Gap: Potential to establish foundations for a European SSH data space ● EOSC Synergies: Position as focal point for EOSC projects interested in innovation ● Policy Alignment: Multiple future research and policy recommendations enabled through ERIC community engagement ● Bottom-up Innovation: Support grassroots innovation versus current top-down approaches 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Environmental Volatility: EOSC's evolving nature and changing EC strategic directions, including evolving status of LUMEN within the federation ● Competition: Existing initiatives at EOSC level and other innovation centres ● Political Shifts: SSH not currently prioritized in EC innovation strategies focusing on hard tech and AI ● Institutional Complexity: Risk of bureaucratic implementation if governance is overengineered

4.8.4. Tetrad Analysis

During the workshop on the EOSC Innovation Centre, we also conducted the McLuhan-inspired tetrad analysis, which revealed potential unintended consequences and important dynamics. The analysis gathered input from the workshop participants on which practices or dynamics the EOSC Innovation centre would enhance, obsolesce, retrieve, or reverse.

Table 21: TETRAD analysis for the EOSC Innovation Centre

Enhances	Obsolesces
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-domain collaboration and co-creation ● Synergies between EOSC projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific silos and disciplinary isolation

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SSH's pivotal role as contributor to other domains Ambition toward addressing grand challenges FAIR as a primary value Intentionality, visibility, and measurability of interdisciplinary knowledge exchange Standardisation of JUST data practices across EOSC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fragmented innovation efforts within individual projects Hyper-specialisation within narrow research niches Innovation as solely commercialisation-focused The vertical separation of EOSC scientific funding
Retrieves	Reverses (leading to...)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renaissance model of integrated knowledge Salon-style knowledge exchange Ideas and discussions across EOSC projects Faith in research as the origin of innovation Productive discussions without a specific agenda 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unfocused competition of agendas Institutional complexity and inertia SSH dominance at expense of other domains Bureaucratic implementation disconnected from real needs Power struggle between disciplines

4.8.5. PESTLE Analysis

Table 22: PESTLE analysis for the EOSC Innovation Centre

Category	Key Points
<i>Political</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunity to enhance SSH role in EU programmes Challenge of national digital sovereignty versus EOSC openness Dynamic changes in EOSC federation structure present a potential barrier
<i>Economic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovation as driver of economic growth Provides a way to avoid reinventing existing solutions Potential exploitation vehicle for white-label platform
<i>Social</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating different knowledge approaches (traditional, indigenous, Western) Public communication opportunity for interdisciplinary research
<i>Technological</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leveraging existing tools across domains Supporting bottom-up versus top-down innovation

<i>Legal</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of intellectual property rights considerations • Introduction of JUST data practices • Potential compliance sandbox function
<i>Environmental</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider federated approach to reduce energy load

4.8.6. Unique Selling Proposition (USP)

The current vision of the Centre has the following USPs:

1. **Serendipity Engine:** Enabling unexpected discoveries through structured cross-domain interaction
2. **Interdisciplinary Salon:** Providing neutral ground for breaking disciplinary boundaries
3. **Innovation Bridge:** Connecting research outputs to societal applications through open science principles (technology transfer)
4. **Innovation within EOSC:** provides a space for innovation and synergies between EOSC projects

4.8.7. Key Takeaways

The following key takeaways can be derived from the work undertaken so far:

- **Vision Crystallisation:** The Centre should focus on extending LUMEN's core mission of enabling cross-domain research innovation through technological affordances and interdisciplinary collaboration
- **Partnership Imperative:** Success depends on finding the right institutional partner(s) who share the vision and can provide sustainability
- **Keep grounding:** We need to talk to other EOSC projects and potential users to avoid a bureaucratic implementation
- **Iterative Development:** The three planned IPLs should be used strategically to co-develop the Centre's concept with stakeholder
- **SSH Data Space Opportunity:** Potential to position the Centre as foundation for a European SSH data space, addressing a critical gap in the current landscape
- **Differentiation through Integration:** The Centre's unique value lies not in competing with existing initiatives but in connecting and amplifying them

4.8.8. Pending decisions

The following key decisions remain open at this point and should be resolved as soon as possible:

1. **Institutional Form:** Will the Centre be a virtual network, hosted service, or distributed federation?
2. **Funding Model:** How will operations be sustained post-LUMEN—through EC funding, institutional support, or service fees?
3. **Scope Boundaries:** Should focus remain on LUMEN outputs or expand to broader EOSC innovation coordination?
4. **Governance Structure:** How to balance community-driven development with operational efficiency?
5. **Success Metrics:** What measurable outcomes will demonstrate the Centre's value and impact?

The current level of uncertainty around the scope of the EOSC Innovation Centre is to be expected, given that the respective task (T7.3) only started in December 2025. The pending decisions identified above will serve as key starting points for the discussion within T7.3.

5. Overview of sustainability modes

The following subsections outline a range of possible sustainability and business models for LUMEN outcomes. Each model is described in terms of its general principles, potential relevance to LUMEN outcomes, and limitations.

For clarity, the models are grouped into two types of sustainability strategies that reflect different time horizons and logics of support:

- **Structural Long-Term Models**, which embed services into institutions, infrastructures, or consortia for stability. ([Institutional & Organisational Support](#), [Membership Models](#), [Community Contribution Models](#), [Integration into Broader Infrastructures](#), [Consortium or ERIC Model](#))
- **Market or Service-Based Model**, which generates income through partnerships, licensing, or value-added services. ([Tiered Access models](#), [Professional services](#), [Usage-Based Pricing](#), [Partnership & IP Monetisation](#))

This typology helps distinguish between approaches that provide structural embedding into stable institutions, and those that explore market-oriented or service-driven income generation.

For the LUMEN project, we deem the following models to be most relevant:

- [Institutional & Organisational Support](#)
- [Integration into Broader Infrastructures](#)

- [Community Contribution Models](#)
- [Tiered Access models](#)
- [Membership models](#)
- [Professional services](#)

5.1. Structural Long-Term Models

5.1.1. Community Contribution Models

Key approaches:

- Volunteer maintenance: Community members contribute code, documentation, or support
- In-kind contributions: Institutions provide server resources, staff time, or expertise
- Crowd-sourced development: Distributed development through hackathons, sprints, or working groups
- Rotating responsibilities: Community members take turns maintaining specific components

Community contribution models leverage collective ownership through voluntary participation rather than financial transactions. This approach relies on the shared interest of community members who benefit from the infrastructure's existence. Contributions can include code development, bug fixes, documentation, user support, or hosting resources. The model often emerges organically in open-source projects and can be formalized through governance structures like technical steering committees or special interest groups. Success depends on maintaining community engagement and distributing workload to prevent contributor burnout.

<p>Suitable for</p>	<p>White-Label Discovery Platform (01) -</p> <p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (03) -</p> <p>Advanced Visualization Tools (07) -</p> <p>AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) (04)-</p>
<p>Why</p>	<p>These outcomes can benefit from distributed expertise and community ownership. Open-source development models allow specialists to contribute in their areas of expertise. The modular nature of these tools enables distributed maintenance without requiring centralized coordination for every component.</p>
<p>Limitations</p>	<p>Unpredictable resource availability; risk of technical debt if contributions are uncoordinated; quality control challenges;</p>

	sustainability depends on maintaining volunteer enthusiasm; critical components may be neglected if not interesting to contributors; difficulty ensuring long-term continuity for essential services.
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5.1.2. Membership models

Key approaches:

- Institutional membership fees: Annual contributions from universities, research organisations, or libraries
- Tiered membership: Different fee levels based on organisation size, GDP, or usage
- Consortium membership: Formal participation in a governing consortium with voting rights
- Disciplinary associations: Fees from learned societies or professional organisations

Membership models create sustainability through formalized stakeholder commitment, where organisations pay annual fees to support infrastructure operations and development. This approach typically involves establishing a legal entity (association, foundation, or AISBL) that manages revenues and ensures accountability to members. Fees can be scaled by institutional size, country GDP, or service usage levels, making the model more equitable. Members often receive governance rights, priority support, or enhanced features in return. The model works best when there is a clear value proposition and strong community identity around the infrastructure.

Suitable for	<p>Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh (O2) -</p> <p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (O3) -</p> <p>Meta-Search Service (O5) -</p> <p>Metrics Service (O6) -</p>
Why	<p>These outcomes benefit from formal stakeholder commitment and structured governance. Membership models ensure stable funding for core operations while giving institutions a voice in strategic direction. The federated nature of these services aligns well with consortium-based governance.</p>

Limitations	Rarely covers full infrastructure costs for technical services; requires significant administrative overhead; risk of free-riding if benefits extend to non-members; difficult to enforce value proposition if services remain fully open; past experience (TRIPLE) showed limited success in generating sufficient revenue.
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5.1.3. Institutional & Organisational Support

Key approaches:

- One of the following entities might see such an added benefit from the platform that they are willing to (co-)fund it:
 - University
 - Learned societies / professional associations
- Institutional hosting/maintenance (single institution like PSNC, or rotating responsibility).
- Creation of a dedicated legal entity/foundation (e.g. like OPERAS).

Institutional or organisational support involves universities, research-performing organisations, or learned societies providing resources for long-term hosting, staffing, and maintenance. In some cases, this may be formalised through a dedicated legal entity (e.g. foundation or ERIC). The advantage is stability and strong community ownership, embedding the infrastructure into the academic ecosystem. The risk lies in over-reliance on a small number of institutions whose priorities or resources may change.

Suitable for	<p>White-Label Discovery Platform (01) -</p> <p>Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh (02) -</p> <p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (03) -</p> <p>Metrics Service (06) -</p> <p>Meta-Search Service (05) -</p> <p>Advanced Visualization Tools (07) -</p> <p>EOSC Innovation Centre (08) -</p>
Why	These outcomes require stable hosting and governance structures that can be supported by universities or research organisations, ensuring long-term continuity.

Limitations	Concentration of responsibility may reduce resilience; sustainability depends on the willingness of institutions to fund beyond their direct benefit.
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5.1.4. Integration into broader infrastructures (EOSC)

Key approaches:

- Embedding into EOSC (Exchange services, FAIR-by-design data contracts)
- Alignment with other long-term infrastructures

Integration into broader infrastructures (e.g. EOSC) secures sustainability through structural embedding into pan-European ecosystems. Services may be included as EOSC Exchange components, supported via FAIR-by-design data contracts, or connected to long-term EU/national research infrastructures. This pathway ensures strong policy alignment and visibility but also creates dependency on EOSC governance and funding mechanisms.

Suitable for	<p>White-Label Discovery Platform (O1) - ,</p> <p>Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh (O2) - ,</p> <p>Meta-Search Service (O5) - , Metrics Service (O6) - ,</p> <p>EOSC Innovation Centre (O8) -</p>
Why	These outcomes act as backbone services that align with EOSC’s interoperability, FAIR, and federated principles.
Limitations	Dependence on EOSC structures and funding; potential loss of autonomy in governance and scope.

5.1.5. Consortium or ERIC Model

A formalised consortium or ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) pools resources from multiple countries and institutions. This model ensures political legitimacy, multi-stakeholder governance, and long-term stability through mixed national contributions.

As of today, there are three potential approaches that would partly fit under this umbrella:

1. Shared governance of LUMEN outputs under the CNRS auspices.
2. Shared governance under the OPERAS auspices.

3. Separate governance for each component, without a global strategy or common branding.

We will undertake further work in T7.2 to explore these approaches in greater detail. In addition, we will consider how the EOSC Innovation Centre (T7.3) will interface with these different options.

Suitable for	<p>Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh (O2) -</p> <p>EOSC Innovation Centre (O8) -</p> <p>White-Label Discovery Platform (O1) -</p>
Why	These outcomes provide backbone services at European scale, aligning naturally with ERIC-type governance.
Limitations	Heavy administrative setup, slow decision-making, and dependency on intergovernmental agreements.

5.2. Market or service-based models

5.2.1. Tiered Access models

Key approaches:

- Freemium: Basic free tier with limited features + premium tier with advanced capabilities
- Dual licensing: Open-source base version + proprietary enterprise version with additional features
- Subscription tiers: Multiple levels of access based on user needs (individual, institutional, enterprise)

Tiered access models create sustainability by differentiating service levels while maintaining open science principles at the base layer. The freemium approach ensures basic discovery and access remains free for all researchers, while premium tiers can include advanced AI features, larger query limits, priority processing, or enhanced visualisation capabilities. Dual licensing allows the core platform to remain open-source (ensuring transparency and community contributions) while generating revenue from enterprise customers who need additional support, security features, or service-level agreements. This model has proven successful in research infrastructures that balance openness with financial sustainability.

Suitable for	<p>White-Label Discovery Platform (O1) -</p> <p>Meta-Search Service (O5) -</p>
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	<p>AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) (04) -</p> <p>Advanced Visualization Tools (07) -</p>
Why	<p>These outcomes have clear differentiation potential between basic and advanced features. Basic discovery, simple queries, and standard visualisations can remain free, while premium tiers offer enhanced AI capabilities, unlimited queries, advanced analytics, or priority support.</p>
Limitations	<p>Risk of creating inequality between well-funded and resource-limited institutions; requires careful balance to avoid restricting essential research capabilities; community resistance if core features become paid; complexity in defining and maintaining tier boundaries.</p>

5.2.2. Professional services

Key approaches:

- Implementation services: Setup, customisation, migration, training
- Managed services: White-label hosting, maintenance, technical support
- Consulting: Data quality improvement, ontology development, workflow optimisation
- Capacity building: Workshops, certification programs, dedicated support

Professional services generate revenue by leveraging expertise rather than restricting access to tools. This model maintains full openness of the software while monetising the knowledge and labor required for effective implementation. Organisations can download and use the open-source platform freely, but many will pay for professional help with deployment, customisation to local needs, integration with existing systems, or ongoing maintenance. This approach aligns well with open science principles as it doesn't create access barriers while providing sustainable revenue through value-added expertise. To be successful, the costs of these services need to be carefully calibrated, which is a topic to be discussed at the 2026 LUMEN IPL.

Suitable for	<p>White-Label Discovery Platform (01) - ,</p> <p>Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh (02) -</p> <p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (03) -</p>
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Why	All LUMEN outcomes require technical expertise for proper implementation. Institutions often lack the internal capacity for deployment, customisation, and maintenance, creating demand for professional services. The complexity of semantic management and federated architectures particularly benefits from expert support.
Limitations	Labor-intensive and difficult to scale; requires maintaining skilled personnel; revenue depends on continuous service delivery rather than product sales; potential conflicts between community support and paid services.

5.2.3. Usage-Based Pricing

Key approaches:

- Pay-per-use: Charges based on queries, API calls, or compute resources consumed
- API licensing: Tiered access levels with rate limits and bulk data access options
- Transactional pricing: Per-analysis, per-visualisation export, per-AI-enhanced query
- Credit systems: Pre-purchased or subscription-based credits for resource-intensive operations

Usage-based pricing scales revenue with actual consumption, making it fair and transparent while keeping basic access free. Users only pay for what they use beyond free quotas, making advanced features accessible to smaller institutions through controlled usage. This model works particularly well for resource-intensive services like AI processing, complex visualisations, or large-scale data exports. API licensing can provide predictable revenue from institutional users while maintaining free access for individual researchers within reasonable limits.

Suitable for	<p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (03) -</p> <p>AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) (04)-</p> <p>Metrics Service (06) - Advanced Visualization Tools (07) -</p>
Why	These outcomes involve computationally expensive operations (AI inference, complex visualisations, large-scale metrics calculations) where infrastructure costs scale with usage.

	Usage-based pricing ensures heavy users contribute proportionally to infrastructure costs.
Limitations	Requires sophisticated metering and billing infrastructure; may discourage experimentation and exploration; creates barriers for unfunded research; complexity in setting appropriate pricing levels; unpredictable revenue streams

5.2.4. Partnership & IP Monetisation

Key approaches:

- Industry collaborations: Joint development, sponsored features, co-funding arrangements
- IP licensing: Proprietary algorithms, specialized ontologies, enhanced methodologies
- B2B integrations: Enterprise connectors, sector-specific solutions (pharma, publishing, government)
- Technology transfer: Commercialisation of innovations through spin-offs or licensing agreements

Partnership and IP monetisation leverages LUMEN innovations for commercial applications while maintaining the open core. This involves strategic collaborations with industry partners who benefit from specialized features or early access to innovations. Revenue can come from licensing proprietary enhancements, creating sector-specific solutions, or joint development of features that serve both academic and commercial needs. This model can include creating specialized ontologies for industry verticals, developing proprietary AI models, or building premium connectors to enterprise systems.

Suitable for	<p>FAIR Semantic Management Space (03) -</p> <p>AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) (04)-</p> <p>EOSC Innovation Centre (08) -</p>
Why	These outcomes generate valuable intellectual property (semantic frameworks, AI models, innovation methodologies) with clear commercial applications. Industry partners in pharma, publishing, and technology sectors have strong interest in these capabilities and resources to invest.

Limitations	Risk of mission drift toward commercial priorities; potential conflicts with open science values; complexity in IP management and licensing; dependence on finding suitable partners; may alienate academic community if not carefully managed.
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5.3. Hybrid Models

Hybrid models combine multiple pathways (e.g. basic EOSC integration + premium services + institutional hosting). They allow diversification of funding sources, reducing dependency on a single stream.

Suitable for	All outcomes.
Why	The diversity of services in LUMEN makes it unlikely that one single model will sustain all outcomes; hybrids provide resilience and flexibility.
Limitations	More complex governance and management, potential for blurred boundaries between open and commercial layers.

6. Preliminary sustainability pathways for Project outcomes

6.1. Sustainability Perspectives for Project Outcomes

The following presents sustainability perspectives per project outcome. They are derived from three sources: 1) the vision documents developed jointly by WP7 and the outcome leads, 2) competitor analysis of existing platforms and infrastructures, and 3) insights from Co-creation workshops (SWOT and PESTLE). Together, these sources outline how sustainability could be envisioned, how it is already practiced in comparable initiatives, and which specific points were discussed during the workshops. These aspects were presented and further debated in the IPL Workshop, with the results summarized in Section [IPL Workshop - Sustainability Pathways](#).

6.1.1. White-Label Discovery Platform based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The White-Label Platform is envisioned as an open-source model offering flexible sustainability options. These may include community-based support structures, commercial service extensions, dual licensing arrangements, membership schemes, and institutional backing. Governance by a legal entity or

through public funding bodies is considered essential to ensure accountability, transparency, and long-term continuity.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable initiatives span both commercial and open domains. Major commercial competitors include *Scopus*, *Web of Science*, and *Dimensions*. Open infrastructures such as *arXiv*, *PubMed*, *CORE*, *Europe PMC*, and *Lens.org* provide relevant reference points for openness and interoperability. Hybrid models like *ScienceOpen*, *JSTOR*, and *Frontiers*, as well as academic networking platforms such as *ResearchGate* and *Academia.edu*, demonstrate diverse sustainability approaches. Non-profit initiatives like *OpenAlex* and *Semantic Scholar* highlight the viability of publicly supported open infrastructures.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Participants expressed a strong and consistent commitment to maintaining the White-Label Platform as open source. It was emphasised that sustainability must extend beyond the lifespan of the LUMEN project. While opinions differed on whether future governance should rely on a community-based/public model or include selective commercial services, there was consensus that service-based opportunities (e.g. custom integrations, analytics, or hosted deployments) could complement open access principles. Integration with EOSC and continued EU or public funding were identified as realistic and desirable pathways for long-term sustainability.

6.1.2. AI Driven Discovery Assistant (AIDA) based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: AIDA's sustainability is closely linked to the White-Label Discovery Platform, forming part of a broader open and interoperable discovery ecosystem. A dual-licensing approach is envisaged, offering free basic access alongside premium or institutional service tiers. Long-term feasibility will depend on managing infrastructure and computational costs, as well as adapting to the fast-paced evolution of AI models and underlying technologies.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable solutions include *IrisAI*, *Consensus*, *Scite.ai*, and *Elicit*, which provide semantic search, evidence synthesis, and citation analysis functionalities. Non-profit models such as *Semantic Scholar* demonstrate the potential of philanthropic and academic funding for sustainability, while *NotebookLM* and *SciSpace* represent personalised, document-grounded AI assistants. Business models across this landscape vary from freemium and subscription-based approaches to API licensing and non-profit or philanthropic support structures.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Workshop discussions identified key sustainability challenges related to high server and model costs, the rapid evolution of AI

technologies, and concerns around bias and hallucination risks. Participants agreed that sustainability must extend beyond project-based funding, exploring models that combine institutional support, service-based revenue, and selective commercial options. Maintaining community trust and transparency in AI processes was seen as essential for long-term adoption and credibility. Integration with EOSC frameworks and alignment with EU trusted AI policies were viewed as realistic and desirable long-term sustainability pathways.

6.1.3. Metrics Service based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The sustainability of the Metrics component should be ensured through institutional or community-driven models, with active involvement of scientific communities as key stakeholders. A clear governance framework is required to define responsibilities and secure maintenance beyond the project's lifetime.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable initiatives illustrate diverse sustainability approaches. *OpenAlex* operates as an open, philanthropy-funded infrastructure, while commercial platforms such as *Web of Science/InCites* and *Scopus/SciVal* rely on subscription-based models offering benchmarking and citation analytics. *Dimensions* represents a hybrid model linking publications, grants, patents, and policy outputs. Together, these examples reflect a divided landscape between open infrastructures and commercial analytics ecosystems.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Workshop discussions highlighted that sustainable development of the Metrics component requires responsible and transparent practices aligned with the principles of CoARA. Participants agreed that long-term viability depends on moving beyond project-based funding, exploring options such as institutional subscriptions, EOSC integration, or strategic partnerships. Community-driven development and clear governance on the scope and use of metrics were identified as essential. Alignment with EU open science and research assessment policies was seen as a key condition for credibility, interoperability, and long-term sustainability.

6.1.4. Advanced Visualisation Tools based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The Advanced Visualisation Tools are planned to be integrated within the White-Label Discovery Platform, making a standalone sustainability model unlikely. Instead, sustainability may be achieved through their inclusion as a premium feature under a dual-licensing approach, ensuring both open access and opportunities for value-added services.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable services include *Lens.org*, which combines public access with paid APIs, and *OpenKnowledge Maps*, which offers open thematic clustering. Tools such as *ResearchRabbit*, *Connected Papers*, and *Inciteful* provide network-based visualisations at free or low-cost access levels, while *Nomic ATLAS* represents a commercial SaaS model using multimodal embeddings. *VOSviewer* illustrates an academic, freely available solution supported through institutional engagement. Overall, sustainability models across this landscape range from fully open infrastructures to commercial software-as-a-service (SaaS) offerings.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Workshop discussions highlighted that sustainability depends on demonstrating domain-specific value, maintaining a simple and intuitive user experience, and ensuring a modular design adaptable to diverse research contexts. Beyond project-based funding, potential pathways include partnerships, EOSC integration, or service-based revenue models. Participants stressed that active community engagement, user co-design, and alignment with open-source principles will be essential for adoption, interoperability, and long-term impact.

6.1.5. Meta-Search based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The sustainability of the Meta-Search component may be achieved through a combination of project-based maintenance, EOSC funding, and community-driven ownership. Integration within EOSC as an Exchange service represents a promising long-term pathway, supporting interoperability and shared access across research infrastructures.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable initiatives include open or publicly funded infrastructures such as *BASE*, *CORE*, *OpenAlex*, and *OpenAIRE*, which exemplify collaborative, open-access approaches to scholarly discovery. AI-driven services like *Google Scholar* and *Semantic Scholar* illustrate sustainability through large-scale corporate or non-profit support, while *Dimensions* and *The Lens* combine subscription-based and hybrid models. These examples demonstrate a spectrum of sustainability pathways, from open infrastructures to commercial ecosystems.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Discussions emphasised that long-term viability requires moving beyond short-term project funding. Potential avenues include integration with EOSC, institutional partnerships, or continued EU support. Key success factors identified were differentiation from existing discovery services, high-quality and interoperable metadata, active community engagement, and clear governance frameworks for data ownership. Participants also highlighted the importance of cost-efficient technical architectures supported by standardised APIs

and semantic alignment to ensure scalability and sustainability within the broader European research ecosystem.

6.1.6. LUMIS based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: LUMIS aims to support the full lifecycle of semantic artefacts through the orchestration of existing open-source tools rather than the creation of new ones. The system is designed primarily for ontology experts and knowledge engineers, ensuring interoperability, FAIR-by-design principles, and alignment with broader EU digital strategies and open science objectives.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable solutions include a mix of open-source and publicly funded initiatives such as *Protégé*, *OntoME*, and *BioPortal*, which offer community-driven models for ontology management. Proprietary and commercial platforms such as *Metaphactory*, *Centree*, *PoolParty*, *Graphologi*, *TopBraid*, *Zazuko*, and *Datavid* represent mature market players with integrated toolchains and enterprise-level support. Hybrid approaches, exemplified by *TopBraid EDG* and similar systems, combine commercial services with elements of open technology and community engagement.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Participants recognised several sustainability challenges, including high operational costs, dependence on external tools, and a relatively small expert user base. It was agreed that sustainability strategies must extend beyond project funding, with potential licensing or service-based models under consideration. Governance and technical architecture are expected to evolve together to ensure flexibility and continuity. Building and maintaining a strong expert community was identified as critical for adoption and long-term viability. Alignment with EOSC and continued EU or public funding were considered realistic and desirable long-term pathways.

6.1.7. EOSC Innovation Centre based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The EOSC Innovation Centre is envisioned as an institutionally maintained entity, either hosted at a fixed site or operating on a rotating basis among LUMEN research and technology organisations. These institutions are expected to serve as core stakeholders, ensuring both strategic alignment with EOSC priorities and continuity of expertise and infrastructure.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable models include *Atos*, which combines commercial service provision with active participation in EU projects and public-private

partnerships, and the *Fraunhofer Clusters*, which operate on a mixed funding model involving public base funding, competitive grants, contract research, and intellectual property commercialisation. The *EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (DIH)* offers a directly relevant precedent—Horizon-funded and providing co-design, technical access, training, and commercialisation support—while maintaining strong connections to EOSC governance and the broader EU innovation ecosystem.

Co-Creation Workshop Insights: Workshop discussions emphasised that sustainability will depend on defining a clear role and differentiation for the EOSC Innovation Centre within the broader EOSC landscape. Governance should promote community-driven participation and cross-domain innovation, avoiding duplication of existing initiatives. Key opportunities include alignment with EU innovation agendas, integration of FAIR and JUST data principles, and partnerships with ERICs and other research infrastructures. Identified risks involve scope expansion, funding volatility, and overlap with parallel EOSC activities, highlighting the need for focused objectives and a stable, diversified funding model.

6.1.8. Federation of Platforms based on Vision, Competitor Analysis and Co-Creation Workshop

Vision: The Federation of Platforms is envisaged as a federated data mesh framework, with PSNC hosting the core services and the broader community maintaining responsibility for data stewardship. The long-term sustainability model is still to be defined, with possible pathways including institutional or public funding, community-based governance, or hybrid models combining both elements.

Competitor Analysis: Comparable initiatives demonstrate a variety of sustainability approaches. Open-source and publicly funded efforts such as *Open Data Mesh*, *EPOS*, and *OSDF* provide models for distributed collaboration, while membership-based federations like *Gaia-X* and *CESSDA* illustrate coordinated governance and funding mechanisms. Non-profit structures such as *IDS* and commercial platforms like *Dawex* show additional routes for sustaining federated data exchange services.

Workshop Insights: Discussions highlighted that governance and technological evolution must progress in parallel to ensure robustness and adaptability. Participants agreed that sustainability cannot depend solely on project-based funding, and that alternative business and governance models must be explored to secure long-term continuity. A strong, engaged community was seen as a central factor for maintaining the federation framework and supporting its ongoing relevance and innovation potential.

6.2. IPL Workshop - Discussing Sustainability Pathways

The information from Section [Sustainability Perspectives for Project Outcomes](#) fed into the preparation of the IPL Workshop in the sense that sustainability models were suggested per outcome based on the information from 1) the vision, 2) competitor analyses, and 3) co-creation workshops. Participants were asked to discuss feasibility and applicability of these models but were also asked to suggest and discuss different ones, if needed. In general, the IPL hybrid Workshop on LUMEN Sustainability Pathways (3 October 2025) brought together partners and stakeholders to co-develop ideas on sustaining LUMEN's outcomes beyond the project's duration. For the complete workshop methodology, please see Section [IPL methodology](#). During the workshop, five discussion groups focused on sustainability pathways for different LUMEN outcomes. Four in-person discussion groups focused on: OS White-Label Platform (including code for metrics, AIDA, visualisations, meta-search service), LUMIS, EOSC Innovation Centre and Federation of Platforms, respectively. The online discussion group focused on a holistic perspective on all outcomes.

6.2.1. Discussion Group: OS White-Label Platform (including metrics, AIDA, Viz, meta-search) - Results

6.2.1.1. Discussion of Sustainability Models

The group discussed several possible sustainability approaches for the Open-Science White-Label (WL) Platform, which brings together metrics, AIDA, visualisation, and meta-search components. Adopting a JSTOR-type paywall was seen as potentially exclusionary: while it could create income, it would reduce the user base and go against LUMEN's open-access principles. In contrast, a "Wikipedia-style" community model—with open editing of metadata, user autonomy, and free membership—was considered more compatible with FAIR and open-science values. Such a model could populate the platform with data and increase engagement if users are successfully brought in. Participants noted that premium or paid tiers might create inequality for who can benefit from the services, and that reliance on EOSC funding would not be viable, as EOSC faces strong competition for resources. They also highlighted the need to clarify who the users are—end-users of final products or organisations purchasing or customising the WL platform—and to define clearly what each group is paying for. It was also questioned whether the WL platform would include a hosting service, as this would affect cost and governance. Possible target models included an ERIC-type membership model, allowing institutional contributions; community gateways similar to OpenAIRE, where organisations can either host their own data or add it to a shared platform; and engagement with public organisations and media companies interested in managing

or enriching their own data. Participants agreed that a combination of models will likely be needed to balance openness, sustainability, and usability.

6.2.1.2. Prioritisation of Feasibility

During the prioritisation exercise, participants indicated (through votes) the models perceived as most feasible - note that only four different workshop participants voted in this exercise:

- Consortium / ERIC model (2 votes)
- Partnership and IP monetisation (2 votes)
- Integration into broader infrastructures (EOSC) (1 votes)
- Tiered access models (1 votes)
- Professional services (1 votes)

Additionally, usage-based pricing was considered relevant for specific components (AIDA, metrics, visualisations), and licensing was mentioned as a supplementary model.

Overall, participants saw a hybrid structure as most realistic—combining institutional or consortium-based funding with professional services and optional monetisation of IP or premium features.

6.2.1.3. General Synthesis

In synthesising their discussion, the group summarised three key points:

- **User and stakeholder groups:** The WL platforms will primarily serve public organisations, research communities (ERICs), and media institutions interested in enriching and hosting their own data.
- **Value and charging principles:** Sustainability requires clarity on what to charge for—hosting, training, or platform customisation were named as potential areas, alongside the possibility of tiered access models and professional service offerings.
- **Governance and model combination:** The platform should combine multiple models (public, community, professional, and tiered access) rather than rely on a single pathway. This would allow flexibility and adaptation to different user needs and funding contexts.

The group agreed that mixing models will be necessary but complex, requiring testing and validation during future pilot phases. LUMEN's WL platforms should

therefore work as an open, modular infrastructure supported by community engagement, institutional partnership, and selective monetisation.

6.2.2. Discussion Group: LUMIS - Results

6.2.2.1. Discussion of Sustainability Models

The group discussed different sustainability options for LUMIS. Participants noted that public and project-based funding, while important for the initial phase, was seen as unstable as a long-term strategy, due to dependency on short-term project cycles and limited continuity once funding ends.

There was consensus that sustainability should instead be based on a combination of models, particularly community contribution and public funding, supported by a stronger organisational framework. Participants underlined the importance of engaging communities early and demonstrating tangible benefits to secure their commitment and input.

The need for comparative analysis of federation models was also raised, to better understand potential synergies, governance requirements, and opportunities for scaling beyond existing communities.

6.2.2.2. Prioritisation of Feasibility

During the prioritisation exercise, participants evaluated the feasibility of different sustainability models for LUMIS by voting on the most realistic options. The results showed a clear preference for Partnership and IP monetisation (5 votes), followed by Community Contribution Models (4 votes). Public and Project-Based Funding and Institutional and Organisational Support each received 3 votes, while Professional Services was also seen as moderately feasible with 3 votes. Membership Models and Usage-Based Pricing both gained 2 votes, and Integration into Broader Infrastructures was noted as an important complementary pathway.

An additional idea raised during the session was the creation of a Tool Marketplace, which could help connect and monetise software components and services developed under the LUMIS framework.

Overall, participants viewed a hybrid sustainability approach as most viable for LUMIS – combining partnerships, community engagement, and institutional support, complemented by targeted professional services and selective monetisation opportunities.

6.2.2.3. General Synthesis

In their final synthesis, participants identified three main points for the LUMIS sustainability pathway(s):

- **Partnerships with service providers were seen as a priority**, potentially forming a marketplace model through which tools and services could be offered collaboratively.
- LUMIS was considered to have **clear value for industry, particularly through possible connections with GRAPHIA and similar platforms**, which could help link research outputs to industrial innovation.
- The **initial development phase of LUMIS should be supported by project funding and community involvement**, with a gradual transition towards self-sustainability depending on user uptake and engagement.

Additional remarks highlighted the potential for paid functionalities—for example, private data options similar to GitHub’s model—and the need to define the core values guiding LUMIS. The group also discussed whether LUMIS could function as a freemium service within the wider LUMEN ecosystem.

6.2.3. Discussion Group: EOSC Innovation Centre - Results

6.2.3.1. Discussion of Sustainability Models

The group discussed the idea of developing an EOSC Innovation Centre as a cross-domain space for experimentation and collaboration within the EOSC environment. Participants proposed that the innovation toolkit should be placed at the centre of this concept, using the results of LUMEN and GRAPHIA as a starting point. The Innovation Centre could serve as a foundational structure based on a data space model, connecting communities, infrastructures, and services across domains. Possible sustainability mechanisms identified included onboarding individual consultants, offering paid training and auditing services, and strengthening industry engagement. These professional activities could generate revenue while maintaining the Centre’s core focus on open and collaborative innovation. The group also discussed whether the Innovation Centre should exist as a virtual or physical space, and agreed that it would likely need to function as a separate organisation providing services to all EOSC stakeholders. This would ensure both neutrality and inclusiveness. Participants identified several relevant frameworks and potential partners, including European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), European Data Spaces, and EOSC DIH, as well as possible collaboration with FitSM e.V. (formerly ITEMO) for process-based innovation management. Overall, the group viewed the EOSC Innovation Centre as a way of linking tools, expertise, and data spaces to support cross-domain innovation in the long term.

6.2.3.2. Prioritisation of Feasibility

During the prioritisation exercise, only two participants voted, indicating which sustainability models they found most feasible for establishing an EOSC Innovation Centre. Each of the following models received one vote: Public and Project-Based Funding, Institutional and Organisational Support, Integration into Broader Infrastructures (EOSC), and Professional Services.

Additional ideas were proposed for consideration beyond the standard models. These included Innovation Management as a Service (providing process support to different projects), Curation and Brokerage functions to facilitate collaboration, and Toolkit Expansion based on the evolving needs of innovation communities.

Overall, while participation in the voting was limited, the discussion suggested that the group viewed a combined approach—anchored in public funding and institutional support, and complemented by professional services and brokerage activities—as the most relevant path for feasibility testing in future phases.

6.2.3.3. General Synthesis

The group identified three main conclusions for the EOSC Innovation Centre concept:

- **The Centre should position itself around innovation management as a service for EOSC stakeholders and projects**, offering structured support and consultancy in managing cross-domain innovation processes.
- **Focus on IPL delivery and innovation activities that are both cross-domain and hands-on**, enabling direct collaboration between scientific and industrial actors.
- **Main focus should remain on cross-domain collaboration**, ensuring that the Innovation Centre acts as a connector rather than a competitor within the EOSC landscape.

Additional comments emphasised the importance of careful positioning to avoid being perceived as competing with EOSC for funding. The Centre should instead be framed as a complementary service provider supporting EOSC's objectives. Participants also noted the potential to pilot use cases to test the concept and validate operational models before scaling up. Opportunities were identified for paid consultancy and training services, which could contribute to the Centre's financial sustainability. The group discussed the idea of renaming the initiative as an "EOSC Cross-Domain Innovation Centre" or "Space", reflecting its collaborative and integrative mission.

6.2.4. Discussion Group: Federation of Platforms - Results

6.2.4.1. Discussion of Sustainability Models

The group discussed sustainability in relation to creating a federation of platforms, exploring how LUMEN could link multiple infrastructures while maintaining a coherent backbone. Participants emphasised the need to define the levels of federation—clarifying whether the federation would focus on data, white-label platforms, or single shared interfaces. This distinction was seen as essential for determining both the governance model and the long-term technical approach. The discussion also underlined that sustainability must be considered not only for the core federated structure but also for its individual components, ensuring that each part of the ecosystem remains viable and maintained over time. In terms of strategic direction, the group identified public funding and cross-domain institutional support as key enablers for the initial phase of the federation. These would provide the stability and coordination needed to establish shared standards, interoperability frameworks, and collaborative governance structures before exploring more complex sustainability mechanisms.

6.2.4.2. Prioritisation of Feasibility

During the prioritisation exercise, only two participants voted on the feasibility of the different sustainability models for the Federation of Platforms. The voting results showed the highest support for Integration into Broader Infrastructures (EOSC) with two votes, followed by Institutional and Organisational Support and Consortium/ERIC Model, which each received one vote.

6.2.4.3. General Synthesis

The group identified three key conclusions regarding the sustainability of a Federation of Platforms:

- **Engaging potential user and stakeholder communities early will be essential to ensure that the federation model reflects real needs and expectations**, as it is difficult to define or decide on the structure and priorities of such a federation without direct community input.
- **Clarifying the benefits of federation, both from a scientific perspective**—demonstrating added value in terms of research outcomes—and from an economic perspective, by achieving efficiencies and economies of scale across shared infrastructures.
- **Comparison of different federation models to assess their potential for synergy and sustainability**. If an effective model can be identified, expansion beyond existing communities should be considered.

Additional remarks highlighted the need to clearly articulate LUMEN's unique selling point (USP) to distinguish the federation from other governance or infrastructure initiatives, and to clarify the relationship between a federation of platforms and LUMEN's overall governance structure.

Overall, the group viewed the Federation of Platforms as a promising but complex outcome, requiring careful definition, strong community engagement, and a clear articulation of its added value within the broader LUMEN ecosystem.

7. Summary of efforts towards exploitation of LUMEN outcomes

7.1. LUMEN exploitation strategy

Exploitation is recognized as the key enabler for the success of the LUMEN project. Hence, all consortium partners are aware of and committed to the exploitation of the project results. With their diverse and complementary research and business contexts and capabilities, they provide relevant exploitation modalities and routes to bring LUMEN results to all targeted user communities.

The exploitation strategy of LUMEN is based upon the "Innovation Management for Practitioners – How to Convert Research into Commercial Success Story" report¹, issued by the EC aiming to tackle the European Paradox of a strong science base but weak innovation performance, and has been tailored to the specificities, needs and results of the project. The project exploitation strategy comprises a range of exploitation activities, among others:

1. The identification of the innovative exploitable assets, whether these are technological components (LUMEN white label discovery platform, LUMEN Chatbot, advanced visualisation tools) or added value services (Federated data sharing governance).
2. The conduction of a thorough market analysis, aimed at the identification of the market towards which LUMEN is targeted, its segmentation, the positioning of current competitors and all corresponding emerging trends.
3. The analytical definition of all possible commercial and non-commercial exploitation models, which have been preliminary identified and are outlined in the following paragraphs.

1

https://publications.europa.eu/resource/cellar/14ff6fe1-023d-4291-8c4d-4ae779aa78a4.0001.02/DOC_1

4. The analytical definition and evaluation of the sustainability and viability of possible business models and alternative solutions that may be followed for the provision of the project solutions and services to the identified stakeholders, including licensing schemes, etc.
5. The establishment of relationships of trust with customers/users early within the project, who can facilitate the quicker adoption of the solutions and provide valuable feedback that can be used in the commercialisation phase.
6. The identification of financial support from diversified funds that can be used to support direct and/or indirect commercial transformation.
7. The use of the Horizon Results Booster service and available templates to streamline the process of developing detailed exploitation plans.

Exploitation Models: The LUMEN consortium recognizes three main exploitation models for the project results: 1) *Commercial exploitation model*, which implies to identify monetisation modes (indirect or direct) with interested stakeholders (customers). 2) *Research exploitation model*, which implies the re-utilisation of the research know-how acquired in future research activities, and 3) *Technological exploitation model*, which implies the re-utilisation of the technological know-how acquired for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them. The exploitation models of the LUMEN project results will depend on three main parameters: a) the nature and interests of the project partners and stakeholders in general, b) the distribution model (commercial or noncommercial) of the project results and c) the distribution of IPR amongst the project partners.

Exploitation Intensity: The exploitation activities will vary in intensity based on the delivery of the project results and the acquisition of R&D know how. The exploitation activities will start with the identification of the innovative exploitable assets of the project. The conduction of a preliminary market analysis identifying potential stakeholders and competitors will intensify prior to the delivery of the intermediate project results with the more analytical definition of all possible commercial and non-commercial exploitation models, and will peak prior to the delivery of the project final results, when the project dissemination activities will also be intensified. Following the project end, the LUMEN consortium will aim at exploiting the project results through business networks and exploitation routes established and defined over the course of the project.

Exploitation Objectives: The exploitation strategy of LUMEN will follow three main stages of expansion with specific short term, medium-term and long-term objectives: 1) *Short-term objectives*: developing the LUMEN solutions focussing on high usefulness and usability; furthermore, verifying and validating the LUMEN results,

concepts, models, tools and services. 2) *Medium-term objectives*: This second stage starts at the end of the project and ends after two or three years, depending on the maturity and completion of the project results. The main objective includes the identification of commercialisation possibilities to bridge the gap from the project's results (TRL level 4-5) to almost market-ready products and services. 3) *Long-term objectives*: Corresponds to the commercialisation of the LUMEN solutions derived from the first and second stage (short-term and medium-term).

7.2. Exploitation activities undertaken so far

As outlined above, step 1 of the LUMEN exploitation strategy was to identify exploitable assets, which is the basis for any exploitation strategy. In the early phase of LUMEN, we identified a set of outcomes which have strong potential for exploitation:

- White Label Platform
- AIDA – AI-Driven-Discovery Assistant
- Meta-Search Service
- Metrics Service
- Advanced Visualisation Tools
- Federation of Platforms – Data Mesh Framework Instantiation
- LUMIS – LUMEN Infrastructure for Semantics
- EOSC Innovation Centre

This list is not definite, and may be expanded or consolidated over the course of the project. The listed outcomes served as the basis for the market analysis and exploration of sustainability pathways reported above. The listed outcomes further serve as candidates for becoming KERs over the course of the project.

The second stage of the LUMEN exploitation strategy - a thorough competitor analysis for all respective outcomes - has been undertaken in the context of the work reported above in the [section on the market analysis](#).

Finally, we have started exploring avenues towards sustainability of the LUMEN outcomes. To this end we conducted a workshop, on which we reported [above](#). A working document with an overview of potential sustainability models, which was used during the workshop, is attached in the appendix. Work on sustainability will continue through newly created task forces within LUMEN dedicated to sustainability (see also section [Conclusions](#)).

Based on the information gathered in 1) the vision, 2) competitor analysis, 3) co-creation workshop (see Section [Sustainability Perspectives for Project](#)

[Outcomes](#)), and 4) IPL workshop (see Section [IPL Workshop - Discussing Sustainability Pathways](#)), we synthesise the following initial ideas regarding sustainability models for the different project outcomes.

7.2.1. Sustainability Models for White-Label Platform including metrics, AIDA, Viz, meta-search

Sustainability for the White-Label Discovery Platform and its components will depend on a hybrid approach that combines institutional or consortium-based support, community engagement, and selective monetisation through hosting, customisation, or professional services. For AIDA, a dual-licensing or freemium model appears most viable, balancing open access with optional premium tiers to offset infrastructure costs. The Metrics Service should build on institutional or community-driven governance aligned with EU research assessment policies to ensure credibility and long-term continuity. The Advanced Visualisation Tools, integrated within the platform, can be sustained through service-based or premium features under open-source governance, supported by modular design and user engagement. For Meta-Search, a federated, community-owned model integrated into EOSC or similar infrastructures offers the most promising pathway, ensuring interoperability, scalability, and shared maintenance.

7.2.2. Sustainability Models for LUMIS

For LUMIS, a hybrid sustainability approach that combines community-driven development with strategic partnerships and institutional support might be best suited. While initial phases may rely on public or project funding, long-term viability should build on collaborative service provision, selective monetisation (e.g. marketplace or freemium features), and active engagement of the expert user community. Alignment with broader infrastructures such as EOSC and continued EU or public collaboration will be key to ensuring continuity, visibility, and interoperability.

7.2.3. Sustainability Models for EOSC Innovation Centre

Sustainability for the EOSC Innovation Centre might rely on a combined institutional and public funding base, complemented by professional and consultancy services that generate revenue through innovation management and training activities. The Centre should act as a cross-domain connector within the EOSC ecosystem, supporting collaborative experimentation and innovation rather than competing for resources. Long-term viability will depend on strategic alignment with EOSC governance and EU innovation programmes, partnerships with Digital Innovation Hubs and ERICs.

7.2.4. Sustainability Models for Federation of Platforms

Sustainability for the Federation of Platforms will depend on a phased, hybrid model combining public and institutional support in the initial stages with community-driven governance and progressive integration into broader infrastructures such as EOSC. Long-term viability will require clear definition of the federation's scope and levels (data, platforms, or interfaces), as well as strong engagement from user and stakeholder communities to ensure relevance and co-ownership. Comparative analysis of federation models and clear articulation of LUMEN's unique value proposition will be essential for positioning the federation as a complementary and scalable framework within the European research ecosystem.

8. Conclusions

This report outlines the activities undertaken by the LUMEN consortium in the first 12 months of the project in terms of market analysis and initial considerations about exploitation and sustainability of LUMEN's outcomes.

The analysis reveals two main conclusions: First, there is strong competition for most of the planned LUMEN services and tools. With the exception of LUMIS, many of LUMEN's outcomes (such as visualisations, discovery chatbots, and search platforms more broadly) face strong competition from existing solutions. While the architectural specifics underpinning LUMEN (such as community-ownership of platforms) are intriguing in abstract terms, it remains unclear how they translate into specific advantages for end users. In particular, the tension between domain-specific searches within domain platforms and the subsequent need for a cross-disciplinary search (meta-search service) introduces substantial complexity in terms of design, governance, and sustainability. In comparison, general purpose platforms such as OpenAlex enable search across all domains while providing filters for more specific queries. Nevertheless, a key benefit of the proposed LUMEN solutions is their complementarity, which will provide a comprehensive environment and streamlined experience for end users.

Second, potential pathways to the sustainability of LUMEN's outcomes are complex and at this stage unclear in their feasibility. On the one hand, this is to be expected at this early stage in the project, in particular since work on some parts of the project (e.g. the Innovation Centre within T7.3) has only started very recently. On the other hand, this is also due to high uncertainty within the EOSC environment. While LUMEN's outcomes should contribute to the service portfolio of EOSC, the exact steps and required actions to embed LUMEN within EOSC are not clear, with the EOSC federation itself constantly evolving.

To answer to these challenges, WP7 will take the following next steps:

- **Strengthen cross-WP collaboration:** We seek to organise multiple internal workshops to bring together knowledge and findings from across WP3 (user needs), WP7 (market analysis), and the technical work packages targeted at design and implementation of services (WPs 2, 4-6). This work will help to address identified alignment needs on planned functionalities.
- **Establish sustainability task forces:** WP7 has introduced task forces that cut across WPs, which are specific to individual outcomes such as the WL platform (and its additional components), the federation of platforms, etc. The task forces will serve as focal points within LUMEN for further developing the sustainability plans for each outcome. They will build on the materials gathered so far and presented in this deliverable, and will produce individual sustainability plans for each key outcome.

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10. Annex

10.1. Working document: overview of sustainability modes

Key Sustainability Models

<p style="text-align: center;">Professional Services</p> <p>Essential Features: Open-source software with paid implementation, hosting, training, and customisation</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserves open access while monetising expertise • Scalable revenue through service delivery • Builds sustainable ecosystem around open tools <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Labor-intensive and difficult to scale beyond core team capacity • Revenue depends on continuous service delivery rather than product sales • Potential conflicts between community support and paid services • Requires maintaining skilled personnel long-term <p>Reference Cases: PKP/Open Journal Systems (free software, paid hosting), WordPress (free CMS, paid options)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Tiered Access Models</p> <p>Essential Features: Basic services free for all users, premium features available through paid subscriptions or institutional licenses</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintains open access while generating sustainable revenue • Scales with user needs and organisational capacity • Familiar model that users understand and accept <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of creating inequality between well-funded and resource-limited institutions • Community resistance if core features become paid • Complexity in defining and maintaining tier boundaries • Requires sophisticated billing and access control systems <p>Reference Cases: Zotero (free basic, paid storage), Consensus (free basic search, premium LLM features)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Community Contribution Models</p> <p>Essential Features: Volunteer maintenance, distributed development, community ownership and shared responsibility</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low financial overhead - relies on passion • High community ownership and long-term commitment • Distributed expertise brings diverse skills and perspectives <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unpredictable resource availability • Quality control challenges - distributed contributors • Critical components may be neglected if not interesting to volunteers <p>Reference Cases: Linux (distributed development), arXiv (volunteer moderators), Wikipedia (community editors)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Institutional & Organisational Support</p> <p>Essential Features: Universities, research organisations, or scientific communities provide stable hosting, staffing, and governance structures</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable, predictable funding and infrastructure • Strong community legitimacy and trust • Embedded in academic ecosystem for long-term continuity <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concentration of responsibility may reduce resilience • Sustainability depends on single institution's priorities • Risk of service interruption if host institution faces budget cuts • May lack resources for major technical upgrades

	Reference Cases: JSTOR (university partnerships), arXiv (Cornell University hosting)
Integration into Broader Infrastructures (EOSC)	
Essential Features: Embedding services into ecosystems (EOSC), ensuring policy alignment and structural support	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strong policy backing and European strategic alignment ● Access to established governance and funding mechanisms ● Interoperability with other European research infrastructures 	Key Limitations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dependence on EOSC structures and funding cycles ● Potential loss of autonomy in governance and scope decisions ● Must comply with complex EU procurement and governance rules ● Risk of service changes due to shifting EU policy
Reference Case: EOSC EU Node? Other options within EOSC?	

Further Sustainability Models

External Grant-Based Funding	
<p style="text-align: center;">Public & Project-Based Funding</p> <p>Essential Features: Recurring competitive grants from Horizon Europe, national agencies, or structural funds</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Large-scale funding for distributed collaborations ● Strong legitimacy through policy alignment <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cyclical funding creates gaps between projects ● Competitive and uncertain - no guarantee of renewal ● Political dependency and changing priorities ● Administrative burden for continuous applications <p>Reference Cases: Horizon Europe projects (LUMEN), EOSC-related initiatives</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Philanthropic & Foundation Funding</p> <p>Essential Features: Support from charitable organisations funding infrastructures as public goods</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Multi-year stability without commercial pressure ● Mission alignment with open science goals ● Less bureaucratic than public funding <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highly competitive and mission-specific ● Time-limited with unclear renewal prospects ● Dependence on single foundation's priorities ● Limited pool of suitable funders <p>Reference Cases: Arcadia Fund, Mellon Foundation, Gates Foundation</p>
Structural Long-Term Models	
<p style="text-align: center;">Membership Models</p> <p>Essential Features: Annual fees from institutions, libraries, or research organisations with governance rights</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Formal stakeholder commitment and ownership ● Predictable revenue stream ● Democratic governance through membership 	<p style="text-align: center;">Consortium or ERIC Model</p> <p>Essential Features: Formalized multi-country resource pooling with intergovernmental agreements</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High political legitimacy and stability ● Mixed national funding reduces single-point failure ● Strong governance framework

<p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rarely covers full operational costs ● High administrative overhead for management ● Free-rider problem if benefits extend to non-members ● Difficulty demonstrating clear value proposition <p>Reference Cases: Crossref, ORCID, GoTriple*</p>	<p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Heavy administrative setup (2-3 years minimum) ● Slow decision-making due to consensus requirements ● Complex legal and bureaucratic processes ● Requires sustained political commitment <p>Reference Cases: CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA, EPOS</p>
<p>Market/Service-Based Models</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Usage-Based Pricing</p> <p>Essential Features: Charges based on actual consumption - queries, API calls, or compute resources</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fair scaling with actual usage ● Transparent and predictable for users ● Covers infrastructure costs proportionally <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Requires sophisticated metering and billing systems ● May discourage research experimentation ● Unpredictable revenue makes planning difficult ● Creates access barriers for unfunded researchers <p>Reference Cases: AWS model, Google Cloud APIs, some research databases</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Partnership & IP Monetisation</p> <p>Essential Features: Revenue from industry collaborations, licensing innovations, or sector-specific solutions</p> <p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leverages research innovations commercially ● Diversifies revenue beyond public funding ● Can accelerate technology development <p>Key Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk of mission drift toward commercial priorities ● Potential conflicts with open science values ● Complex IP management and legal requirements ● May alienate academic community if poorly managed <p>Reference Cases: Technology transfer offices, industry-academia partnerships</p>

10.2. Table of competitors considered during competitor analysis

The below table lists all competitors considered for each outcome. Competitors shaded in green were selected by the outcome lead. Competitors shaded in blue were added by TK and LD. Competitors shaded in violet were considered highly relevant in general but not in particular (e.g. because they are a methodology rather than a service).

White Label Platform / Discovery Platforms (O1)	Federation of Platforms - Data Mesh Framework Instantiation (O2)	FAIR Semantic Management Space (O3)	AI-Driven Discovery Assistant (O4)	Interdisciplinary Meta-Search Service (O5)	Metrics Service (O6)	Advanced Visualisation Tools (O7)	EOSC Innovation Centre (O8)
Scopus	Dataverse	Ontotext	Iris.ai	BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine)	OpenAlex	OpenKnowledge Maps	Atos
Web of Science	CKAN	GraphDB	Consensus.app	SSH Open Marketplace?	Altmetric.com	ResearchRabbit	European Digital Innovation Hubs
OpenAlex	EUDAT	Protégé	Scite.ai	EBSCO	Data Metrics Badge by DataCite	Nomic ATLAS	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
Semantic Scholar	Protégé	Elixir	elicit	CORE	WoS/InCites	Litmaps	Fraunhofer Innovation Clusters
Dimensions	Databricks	Fair-Impact	Litmaps	Google Scholar	Scopus/SciVal	R Shiny	EOSC DIH

		Initiative			(Elsevier)		
Academia.edu	Open Data Mesh Platform	FairSpace by The Hyve	Semantic Scholar	OpenAlex	Dimensions	Python Matplotlib	OPERAS Innovation Lab
JSTOR	Gaia-X	Discuss Data	NotebookLM	OpenAIRE Explore	Crossref	GraphPad Prism	
arXiv.org	ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation)	PoolParty	ChatPDF	Dimensions	PlumX	Origin Lab	
Frontiers	EPOS (European Plate Observing System) - Dataportal	BioPortal	SciSpace	Semantic Scholar	PURE (Elsevier)	Dimensions.ai	
PubMed	DataONE (Data Observation Network for Earth)	Metaphactory	ScholarScy	ScienceOpen	ERIHPlus	Connected Papers	
Google Scholar	Open Science Data Federation (OSDF)	Centree	ResearchGPT	The Lens		Lens.org	
ResearchGate	Dawex Data Exchange	Pollparty Semantic Suite	SciSummary	B2FIND (EUDAT)		Scopus / SciVal (Elsevier)	
CORE	International Data Spaces (IDS)	Graphology	ExplainPaper	OAIster		VOSviewer	
Lens.org	OpenAIRE	OntoME	Perplexity.ai	Scilit		Inciteful.xyz	
ScienceOpen	CESSDA (Consortium of European Social	Palantir Ontology Manager	ScholarAI	Matilda.science		SciSight	

	Science Data Archives)						
Europe PMC	CLARIN	TopBraid EDG	PaperBrain			BibGraph	
bioRxiv	GEOSS (Global Earth Observation System of Systems)	Zazuko Ontology Manager	AskYourPDF				
medRxiv		Graphite					
Overton.io		Kaiasm OntoKai					
BASE (Bielefeld Academic Search Engine)		Laces Ontology Manager					
WorldWideScience.org		Intelligent Taxonomy Manager					
Zendy		Datavid Ontology Management					
CORE discovery							

10.3. Competitor analysis for white label platform

Identification		Product/Service Offerings		
Product/Service Name	Link	Most relevant functions and features	Added value of platform for stakeholders	Relevance for consideration within LUMEN
	<i>URL for the product/service</i>		<i>What feature/function is unique/outstanding? How would you describe the USP (Unique Selling Proposition) of the platform/service?</i>	<i>What can we learn or should take into consideration for the LUMEN solutions?</i>
Scopus	https://www.scopus.com/	<p>- Search abstracts and citations of "peer-reviewed literature including scientific journals, books, and conference proceedings."</p> <p>It claims to provide "a comprehensive overview of worldwide research output in the fields of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities.", although there are other databases with larger coverage.</p>	- Content is added after evaluating sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Search interface that caters both for casual and expert users - Flexible options for exporting search results and API access - Easy way of discovering citing and cited articles

Web of Science	https://www.webofscience.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Abstract and citation database of scientific literature - Multidisciplinary: life sciences, health sciences, technology, social sciences, arts and humanities - Content from journals, books, conference proceedings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - JIF (Journal Impact Factor), one of the most prestigious indicators for measuring the impact of science, is exclusive to this platform - Content is added after evaluating sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A single search interface for all content - Multiple search options - Long and diverse list of metadata - Options for users to save lists of results and defining alerts - Links to full text - Diverse and consolidated bibliometric indicators
OpenAlex	https://openalex.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open access catalog of scientific works, authors and organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Free API - Complete dataset free under the CC0 license 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehensive and inclusive, especially for works in other languages and the Global South - Diverse list of bibliometric indicators
Semantic Scholar	https://www.semanticscholar.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI-based academic search engine - Citation context & influence mapping - Author pages, paper summaries, topic classification - Filters: field, publication type, method, dataset etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced discovery via AI (summary, citation context) - Focus on relevance over volume - Structured filtering by domain-specific needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benchmark for smart filtering & semantic enrichment - Valuable model for AI-assisted literature tools
Dimensions	https://app.dimensions.ai/discover/publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Database of publications, datasets, clinical trials, grants, patents, policy documents and reports - Partially free access under registration - Offers short AI summaries - integration with "Papers" app from same company for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "world's largest collection of linked research data" - link with patents is important for some 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diversity of research outputs - "Dimensions is the only database that links publications and citations with grants, patents, clinical trials, datasets, and policy papers" - Search for publications & datasets is free, while grants, patents, trials, policy documents, and reports require a subscription.

		managing references and PDFs		
Academia.edu	https://www.academia.edu	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research networking (profile, follow, upload papers) - Search & alerts for articles - Analytics: who viewed your paper (premium) - Bulk download (premium) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User engagement via alerts & metrics - Networking across disciplines - Discovery of similar work & scholars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Notification-based engagement (caution: too many) - Example of what to avoid: over-commercialisation - Useful features: alerts, interest-based prompts
JSTOR	https://www.jstor.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full-text access to academic journals, books, and primary sources - Thematic collections, image search (Artstor), text analysis tool - Search by content type, subject, or institution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deep archive access across humanities, social sciences, and more - Integration with Artstor for visual materials - Access via institutions or personal accounts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UX elements (e.g. reading lists, collection curation) - Content structuring & stable citation models - Sustainability model for access in low-resource settings
arXiv.org	https://arxiv.org	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preprint repository for scientific articles (esp. physics, math, CS) - Advanced search and browse features - Author affiliation linking & versioning - Daily submission feeds and export options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early and open access to current research - Community-curated, moderated by domain experts - Persistent and citable identifiers (arXiv ID) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open access infrastructure model - Supports early dissemination workflows - Strong version control and transparency features

Frontiers	https://www.frontiersin.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Access publishing with collaborative peer review - AI-supported editorial platform (AIRA) - Article-level metrics, Loop network, alerts - Search by article, topic, journal, author etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparent, interactive peer review - Research impact tracking - Strong academic community support - AI tools for editorial processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advanced Open Science model with integrated tools - Strong UX/UI and search features as benchmark for LUMEN - Community-based and data-rich publishing model
PubMed	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - academic literature search (biomedical + life sciences) - citation management - organises research using MeSH - Provides specialised search tools (e.g. for clinical queries, systematic reviews, and evidence-based practice resources) - free + searchable database for citation & abstracts, full-text may be linked 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - open access database - domain-specific search options, advanced search 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - status subsets, indicating current state of entry (e.g. just submitted vs. already tagged with MeSH terminology) - indexation with specific + consistent set of terminology
Google Scholar	https://scholar.google.com/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academic search for articles, patents, theses, etc. - Google Scholar Profiles with citation metrics (h-index etc.) - Library, Alerts & Metrics features - Wide-ranging full-text linking and abstract views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broad academic content coverage - Very familiar Google-style usability - Automatic citation tracking & alerts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benchmark for simplicity and broad appeal - Profile & notification tools useful for engagement features - Relevance-based ranking of content

ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researcher profiles, networking, private messaging - Search for publications, researchers, jobs, funding - Statistics: reads, citations, recommendations - Q&A community, job board, mobile app 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Massive global researcher network - Research impact tracking and engagement tools - Platform for scientific job and product advertising 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model for social-academic platforms - Recommendations & researcher engagement - Valuable integration of networking and search
CORE	https://core.ac.uk/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aggregates 176+ Mio. Open Access articles - Free API, Dataset, FastSync access - CORE Recommender & Discovery - Repository Dashboard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large global OA dataset - Discovery tools & services for researchers/institutions - Free and premium data services (e.g. FastSync) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong content aggregation & enrichment model - Useful for building linked open scholarly infrastructures
Lens.org	https://www.lens.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scholarly and patent search with advanced filtering and analytics - Citation and influence mapping - Export options and personal workspaces - Biological sequence search 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Free access to enriched scholarly, patent, and sequence data - Integration of diverse resource types (citations, patents, biosequences) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rich search and analysis tools - Linking across data types - Strong filtering and export options - Lessons for TRIPLE: clear use-case based design
ScienceOpen	https://www.scienceopen.com	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discovery platform with 88M+ records - Public peer review and post-publication commenting - Open Access hosting and publishing - Advanced search, export, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparent and interactive post-publication review - Promotes visibility and community curation - Supports Open Science workflows and integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model for transparency in peer review - Strong filtering & metric-based visibility - Flexibility for integration into institutional publishing

		metrics & DOI creation		
Europe PMC	https://europepmc.org/	<p>Integrated Search: including abstracts, full-texts, and preprints.</p> <p>Open Access Full Text: Over 9 million full-text articles, including links to external sources.</p> <p>Advanced Search Filters: Boolean operators, metadata filters (type, date, access status).</p> <p>Citation Tools: Citation tracking, export options (RIS, BibTeX).</p> <p>Annotations & Text Mining: Named entity recognition (e.g., genes, diseases); API access; machine-learning-ready datasets.</p> <p>Preprint Inclusion: Aggregates from major repositories for up-to-date research.</p> <p>Grant Linking: Connects publications with research grants.</p> <p>Programmatic Access: RESTful APIs and R package for automated workflows.</p>	<p>Researchers & Academics</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comprehensive Discovery: Unified access to peer-reviewed articles, preprints, and datasets. - Open Access Focus: Enables unrestricted access to full-text scientific literature. - Research Impact: Tools for citation tracking and grant linkage support CV building and funding applications. <p>Practicians</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence-Based Practice: Quick access to clinical research and reviews. - Up-to-Date Information: Preprints and recent publications aid real-time decision-making. <p>Data Scientists & Developers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Machine-Readable Data: Annotated corpora and APIs support text mining and AI development. - Tool Integration: Open infrastructure for embedding in workflows and platforms. <p>Funders & Policy Makers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grant Monitoring: Tracks publications linked to specific funding. - Open Science Compliance: Supports transparency and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supports Open Science workflows and integration; - Community-based and data-rich publishing model; - Flexible options for exporting search results and API access; - Multiple search options

			open-access mandates.	
Overton.io	https://www.overton.io/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Database of grey literature and policy documents (+18 million in total) - Enables tracking of academic literature in policy documents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enables analysis and tracking of policy documents and use of academic literature therein 	The specific data type "policy document" might be relevant, but maybe not feasible in terms of implementation.

